
Final PhD Thesis Report

METAPRO

Metagenomics and genomic approaches for the prevention of the spread of plazomicin resistance in animals, humans and the environment

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INTRODUCTION

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1. PhD Project team composition

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2. Abstract

Aminoglycosides, and more specifically next-generation aminoglycosides, offer some hope in the current times of antimicrobial resistance. However, the emergence of acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases jeopardises the use of this antibiotic class, as they confer high-level of resistance to virtually all aminoglycosides. Prevalence of this resistance mechanism is considered low in Europe, as only around a one percent of all the isolates carry any of the resistance enzymes comprised in this group. The main objective of the present project is further evaluating the presence of this resistance mechanisms in complex environments to investigate the role of non-pathogenic bacteria in the acquisition and maintenance of these genes.

Our results show that the prevalence of acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases is higher than expected. Interestingly, instead of detecting the highly reported enzymes *armA* or *rmtB*, we detected less reported enzymes like *rmtD*, *rmtF*, *rmtG* and *npmA*. We focus our work on *npmA*, as is found in humans and animals in a high prevalence and because it has been described as the enzyme with the broader aminoglycoside-resistance spectrum. It was found in different genetic environments, plasmidic and chromosomic, and seem to be different in the different settings where it has been recovered. In a more comprehensive study of the distribution of the gene we saw that is already spread worldwide and that up to nine different variants of the gene can be found. However, current metagenomic analysis did not allow for the detection of the specific reservoirs of the gene in the different sources. Therefore, we have tested the possibility of detecting the gene using a combination of fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH) with fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS) to be able to isolate single cells that throw some light on the bacterial species and genetic elements that maintain *npmA* in the different environments. Our preliminary results on a control model show promising results as around a fifty percent of the *npmA*-containing cells can be sorted effectively. Finally, we evaluated the effect of the aminoglycoside apramycin, an antibiotic in the development pipeline to be the next one released for its use in humans. We observed that apramycin application has no effect on the bacterial composition but strongly selects for apramycin resistance genes *aac(3)-IV* and *npmA*, that seem to be a common component of the gut microbiome.

Overall, the present study exhibits that 16S rRNA methyltransferases, and specifically *npmA*, might be a great concern once old and next-generation aminoglycosides start to be used more widely as their prevalence might be underestimated. Understanding which bacteria and genetic elements act as reservoirs can help us design strategies to limit their spread to pathogenic bacteria and prevent the inefficacy of all the aminoglycosides yet to come. A great example of the actual problematic is the use of the next-generation aminoglycoside apramycin, that greatly selects for apramycin resistance genes and promotes their mobilisation, so it can become ineffective in a short time after its approval for human use.

3. Introduction and Objectives

1.- Antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance

The discovery of antibiotics is arguably one of the most important milestones in human history. The application of these compounds revolutionised medicine by not only curing life-threatening infections, but also enabling many modern medical procedures such as organ transplants and cancer chemotherapy (Hutchings *et al.*, 2019). The term antibiotic refers to any natural, synthetic, or semi-synthetic substance, that is capable to inhibit or kill susceptible bacteria and other organisms at low concentrations (Singleton and Sainsbury, 2006).

Based on this definition, the first known antibiotic in history is the synthetic arsenic-based drug Salvarsan, a molecule developed by Paul Ehrlich in 1907 to treat syphilis (Williams, 2009). Subsequently, Gerhard Domagk conducted a systematic screening of a library of synthetic compounds and discovered Prontosil Red, the first broad-spectrum antibiotic. Prontosil was the first of a long list of antibiotic molecules now known as sulfonamides (Sneider, 2001). However, with the discovery of the first natural antibiotic penicillin by Alexander Fleming in 1928, the paradigm changed (Fleming, 1929). The screening of synthetic compounds was replaced by the study of microbes to find novel antimicrobial agents, initiating the “Golden Age” of antibiotic discovery. In the period between 1940 and 1960, many different antibiotic classes were discovered, forming the origin of most of the compounds that are used in clinical practice nowadays. After this period, the identification of novel antibiotic substances became increasingly difficult, which in turn forced a shift in the innovation in antibiotic discovery. Now the focus was on creating synthetic versions of the natural compounds with fewer pharmacological drawbacks, initiating what has been called the “Medicinal Chemistry Era” (Brown and Wright, 2016). However, the extensive use done of all antibiotic molecules since their discoveries promoted a high prevalence of antibiotic resistant bacteria, leading to the “Antibiotic Resistance Era”, in which many antibiotics are ineffective against common bacterial infections (Hutchings *et al.*, 2019).

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of microorganisms to persist in the presence of antimicrobial drugs (Abushaheen *et al.*, 2020). Since most of our antibiotics are naturally produced by microorganisms, it is believed that the origin of antibiotic resistance in many cases comes from the antibiotic producing bacteria themselves, as they needed a defensive system to survive in the ecological niche where they released the antibiotic (Perry *et al.*, 2016). However, the massive use of the antibiotics has accelerated this natural process. Shortly after a new antibiotic was introduced for clinical use, resistance emerged, resulting in a continuously smaller antibiotic arsenal. In addition, the innovation in the field of antibiotic discovery is scarce due to the high restrictions of the pharmaceutical regulations and the limited economic profit. Coupled with the increasing levels of resistance, there is a threat of a “Post-Antibiotic Era” in which the medical situation may regress to a time when antibiotics were not yet discovered (Kwon and Powderly, 2021).

Antimicrobial resistance can be obtained through three main mechanisms: i) reduction of the intracellular concentration of the antimicrobial agent either by reduced permeability of the molecule or increased expulsion out of the cell; ii) antibiotic inactivation either through the modification of the antimicrobial structure or by its enzymatic hydrolysis; and iii) modification of the target of the antimicrobial agent by genetic or post-transcriptional changes. Bacteria can be resistant through any

of these mechanisms in an intrinsic or an acquired form. Intrinsic resistance is the ability of a certain species to be resistant to an antibiotic because of its inherent functional or structural capabilities (Blair *et al.*, 2015). On the other hand, some individuals of a given species can acquire resistance through spontaneous mutations or via the acquisition of foreign genetic material from other microorganisms. This latter phenomenon is known as horizontal gene transfer (Arnold *et al.*, 2022). Horizontal gene transfer allows for a rapid spread of resistance genes to susceptible bacteria and can be driven by three main mechanisms: i) transformation, a mechanism in which the bacterium captures free DNA from the environment and integrates it into its genome (Krüger and Stingl, 2011); ii) conjugation, which consists in the transfer of genetic material, mainly in the form of plasmids, through a type IV secretion system (Thomas and Nielsen, 2005); and iii) transduction, a mechanism that involves the transfer of bacterial DNA via infection with bacteriophages (Torres-Barceló, 2018).

2.- Aminoglycosides

In 1944, Selman Waksman and Albert Schatz discovered streptomycin by screening different cultures of soil bacteria. Streptomycin was not only the first antibiotic effective against tuberculosis but also the first of a large group of antibiotics known as aminoglycosides (Schatz *et al.*, 1944). Using the same methodology, other compounds with similar structures were isolated as products from bacteria of the *Streptomyces* and *Micromonospora* genera and introduced into clinical practice during the following decades. Aminoglycosides were widely used in the treatment of several bacterial-caused diseases, but their toxicity and the emergence of antibiotics with a broader activity made aminoglycosides recede in the therapeutic hierarchy. However, the increasing resistance to first line antibiotics and the advance in the knowledge of aminoglycosides and their resistance has restored the interest in this class. They are now considered a critically needed last resort antimicrobial group by the World Health Organization (WHO) and by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), what has led to a relaunch of the development of novel aminoglycosides in the last years (WHO, 2019; OIE, 2019).

2.1.- Aminoglycoside classification

The term “aminoglycoside” was given based on the general chemical structure of this group of antimicrobial agents. Their backbone consists of an aminocyclitol ring that can be saturated with amine and hydroxyl substitutions, and it is linked to one or more amino sugars through glycosidic linkages (Benveniste and Davies, 1973). They can be classified into two main groups based on their structural core. The first group is comprised by the aminoglycosides that present 2-deoxystreptamine (2-DOS) as the aminocyclitol moiety, while the other group includes all the aminoglycosides that have a different central aminocyclitol ring. A further sub-classification of the 2-DOS group is necessarily made based on the position of the glycosidic bonds. Three structural subgroups are then formed: mono-substituted 2-deoxystreptamines, 4,5-disubstituted 2-deoxystreptamines, and 4,6-disubstituted 2-deoxystreptamines. Despite the shared activity of protein-mistranslation, the antimicrobial potency and the ability to evade resistance mechanisms vary between the different structural groups.

There is one structurally unique aminoglycoside belonging to the 2-DOS aminoglycosides group, which is apramycin. This compound is the only one that presents the 2-deoxystreptamine aminocyclitol ring monosubstituted in position 4. Apramycin is produced by various actinomycetes of the genus *Streptomyces* but also by other bacteria from other genera such as *Sacchalopolyspora* (Matt *et al.*, 2013).

The 4,5-disubstituted 2-DOS were first described in 1949 and are represented by neomycin, the first and the most important member of this class. This group is made up of several naturally occurring agents isolated from bacteria of the genus *Streptomyces*, including -but not limited to- the aforementioned neomycin, paromomycin, lividomycin and butirosin. Another member of this group, ribostamycin, isolated from *Streptomyces ribosidificus*, is thought to be the precursor of the 4,5-2-DOS aminoglycosides (Kudo and Eguchi, 2016). Additionally, some *Micromonospora* spp. have been found to produce neomycin and paromomycin. Interestingly, butirosin can be produced by species of the genus *Bacillus*.

The 4,6-disubstituted 2-DOS class contains most of the clinically useful aminoglycosides. Supported by this fact, some of the members of this group have been used as a template for the design of new semisynthetic agents (Park *et al.*, 2013). The group can be subdivided into two families, the kanamycin family and the gentamicin family. The kanamycin family, discovered in 1957 from a *S. kanamyceticus* culture, includes the naturally produced compounds kanamycin, bekanamycin, and tobramycin. This family has led to the creation of dibekacin, amikacin, and arbekacin as semi-synthetic derivatives. The other family is constituted by the gentamicin compounds. These agents were first isolated from cultures of *M. purpurea* -which was later renamed to *M. echinospora*- in 1963. Very similar compounds were described later from cultures of other species of *Micromonospora* spp. The main naturally produced aminoglycosides related to gentamicin are gentamicin C, gentamicin B, micromomicin, sisomicin, and geneticin. Netilmicin and isepamicin are semi-synthetic derivatives that belong to this group. Recently, plazomicin has been added to this list (Magnet and Blanchard, 2005; Eljaaly *et al.*, 2019).

The non-2-DOS aminoglycosides represent the minority of all aminoglycoside compounds discovered to date. Except for streptomycin, which possesses a streptidine ring as the central aminocyclitol, the agents belonging to this group are not as clinically relevant as the 2-DOS aminoglycosides. Other main representatives that do not use 2-deoxystreptamine as central ring are spectinomycin and fortimicin, presenting actinamine and fortamine respectively (Piepersberg, 1995).

2.2.- Aminoglycoside mode of action

The major target of aminoglycosides is the 30S subunit of bacterial ribosomes. It has been identified that they bind to the 16S rRNA residues that comprise the aminoacyl site (A-site), leading to a loss of translational accuracy and, subsequently, to cell death (Magnet and Blanchard, 2005; Jana and Deb, 2006). Some members of the class can also impact protein synthesis by inhibiting initiation or by blocking elongation (Wilson, 2014). To be able to bind to the ribosome, aminoglycosides must enter the cell. Although these antibiotic-molecules bind electrostatically to the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria or to the exterior of the cell wall of Gram-positive bacteria, their uptake and diffusion across the cytoplasmic membrane requires energy generated from an oxygen-dependent process, the energy dependent phase I (EDP-I) (Taber *et al.*, 1987). Consequently, these antibiotics are less active in anaerobic conditions. Aminoglycoside uptake is a self-promoted process that requires a proton-motive force and involves a drug-induced disruption of Mg^{2+} bridges between adjacent lipopolysaccharide molecules (Mingeot-Leclerq *et al.*, 1999). Once in the cytosol, aminoglycosides bind to the A-site in the small subunit of the ribosomes, which is comprised of a portion of helix 44, amongst others. As it has been extensively described, the fidelity of translation depends mainly on the correct formation of the initiation complex, which involves the mRNA codon, the appropriate tRNA anticodon,

and subsequent proofreading during the elongation step. When a cognate tRNA-mRNA complex is formed, residues A1492 and A1493 are flipped out from helix 44, allowing this configuration to discriminate between correct or erroneous complexes (Carter *et al.*, 2000). Aminoglycoside binding takes place in a pocket formed by various residues of helix 44 which are the universally conserved nucleotides A1492 and A1493, and the prokaryotic-specific nucleotide A1408. This aids in their selective activity against the bacterial as opposed to the eukaryotic ribosome (Jana and Deb, 2006).

It has been biochemically elucidated that when a 2-deoxystreptamine aminoglycoside binds to this pocket, it causes a flip out of residues A1492 and A1493, similar to the one that occurs when there is a cognate mRNA-tRNA complex. Therefore, there is no discrimination between cognate and non-cognate complexes, which disrupts the translation at the elongation level leading to the accumulation of aberrant proteins. These faulty proteins may eventually be inserted into the cell membrane, altering the permeability and facilitating subsequent aminoglycoside entry in the so-called energy dependent phase II (EDP-II) (Carter *et al.*, 2000).

In the case of non-2-DOS aminoglycosides, their interaction with the 30S ribosomal subunit presents some differences. Streptomycin binds to the A site, however, in contrast to the 2-DOS-aminoglycosides, it does not interact only with residues from helix 44 but also with residues from adjacent domains. It has been previously proposed that an interaction between helix 27 and helix 44 leads to two different ribosomal conformations and the balance of these conformations could be involved in the translational proofreading. This balance appears to be disturbed by the binding of streptomycin. The binding of both spectinomycin and hygromycin B to the 30S subunit inhibits the translocation of the peptidyl-tRNA from the A site to the P site (Peptidyl site), although hygromycin B also causes miscoding, but at a lower level than DOS-aminoglycosides (Carter *et al.*, 2000).

In addition, it has been shown that some aminoglycosides, such as gentamicin and neomycin, bind to helix 69 of the 23S rRNA in the large ribosomal subunit. Binding at this site inhibits the ribosomal recycling process, a necessary step in which the two subunits separate from each other after the termination phase of protein synthesis to be able to bind new mRNA (Wang *et al.*, 2012).

2.3.- Aminoglycoside therapeutic indications

Aminoglycosides are broad-spectrum antimicrobials that exhibit potent bactericidal activity. Only two exceptions are found in this antibiotic class, spectinomycin and kasugamycin, that act bacteriostatically by inhibiting the translocation step. The action of the aminoglycosides is in all cases concentration-dependent and presents a prolonged post-antibiotic effect. Advantages of aminoglycosides include their remarkable chemical stability, rarity of allergic reactions, low cost compared to other agents and the possibility of synergistic activity when used in combined therapy with other antibiotics (Eliopoulos, 1989; Tsai *et al.*, 2013). The combination of all these features made aminoglycosides one of the core classes in the early ages of antibacterial chemotherapy. However, some of their disadvantages such as their poor oral absorption, the lack of activity against anaerobic bacteria, the rapid clearance through the urinary tract and, most importantly, the secondary effects that they exhibit due to the activity of certain aminoglycosides on eukaryotic cells, led to their discontinuation from primary use (Craig, 2011). Nevertheless, a better understanding of all these adverse effects in the last years has led to a safer and more effective use of these antimicrobials. This, combined with the emergence of high resistance levels to other antibiotic compounds, has put aminoglycosides back on the focus of interest.

Aminoglycosides have proven efficacy against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive microorganisms. The class is especially active against diverse members of the Enterobacteriaceae family, such as *Escherichia coli* or different species of *Klebsiella* or *Enterobacter*. They also show activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* or *Acinetobacter* spp., but to a lesser extent. The class is also active against several Gram-positive bacteria, such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, including vancomycin and methicillin resistant variants, or different *Mycobacterium* species. Members of this antimicrobial group present good activity against *Yersinia pestis* and *Francisella tularensis*, etiologic agents of the biothreat diseases pneumonic plague and tularemia, respectively. Since aminoglycosides require active transport to enter the cell, they are inactive against anaerobic bacteria. Additionally, they show poor efficacy against *Streptococcus* spp. and *Enterococcus* spp. (Krause *et al.*, 2016).

Aminoglycosides are often administered as combination therapy to enhance their potency, to enlarge the spectrum of activity and to prevent the development of resistance through synergistic interactions. They are commonly used along with the β -lactam class based on the hypothesis that the disruption of the bacterial cell wall caused by β -lactam antibiotics facilitates the entrance of aminoglycosides. This synergy has been proven in *in vitro* and *in vivo* models, but strong clinical evidence supporting this statement is still needed, since conflicting data has been presented. Nevertheless, other antibiotics that affect the cell wall can be co-administered with an aminoglycoside to treat multidrug resistant bacteria or to improve therapy against bacteria naturally resistant to aminoglycosides because of reduced uptake (Tamma *et al.*, 2012; Zavascki *et al.*, 2013).

As mentioned before, the major drawback of the use of aminoglycosides is the associated toxicity. Nephrotoxic and ototoxic effects have been clearly linked to the clinical application of this group antibiotic of (Fischel-Ghodsian, 2005; McWilliam *et al.*, 2016). In addition, neurotoxicity due to aminoglycoside administration has been also reported, but the cases are scarce (Grill and Maganti, 2011). Between 20 and 30% of the patients undergoing aminoglycoside treatment present renal signs of damage. They usually manifest as a non-oliguric renal dysfunction with increased levels of urea and creatinine in plasma, electrolyte alterations and the presence of diverse metabolites in the urine, such as proteins or glucose. This medical condition results from the accumulation of aminoglycosides in the epithelial cells of the proximal tubule, where they produce changes that lead to cell death and impairment of their usual functions, such as ion exchange and nutrient absorption. This disruption is reversible in most of the cases since the cells of the proximal tubule are replaced by normal cell proliferation (Mingeot- Leclercq *et al.*, 1999; Lopez-Novoa *et al.*, 2011). Ototoxicity is probably the most important disadvantage of the use of aminoglycosides. Produced by the interruption of mitochondrial ribosomes, aminoglycoside-associated ototoxicity can have two different manifestations according to the affected cells: vestibulotoxicity or cochleotoxicity. Clinical signs vary, with balance disorder being the main sign for vestibulotoxicity and hearing loss for cochleotoxicity. The manifestations of ototoxicity are a major concern because of the high prevalence and irreversibility (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, some studies have pointed out a genetic predisposition to ototoxicity by specific ribosomal polymorphisms that might be a crucial factor when considering ototoxic effects. Finally, some neurotoxic effects have been associated with the use of aminoglycosides, with neuromuscular blockade being the principal effect observed. Reports of these effects are very rare and, in most cases, have been linked to doses higher than the clinically used dose (Grill and Maganti, 2011). Several factors influence the emergence of these toxic effects such as the type of aminoglycoside used, the dosage and length of the treatment, the combination with other drugs, the age of the patient or the genetic predisposition (Paterson *et al.*, 1998; Xie *et al.*, 2011). The

understanding of all the potential risks of the aminoglycosides has led to a better and safer use of them. For instance, higher doses or treatment maintained over a longer period was more likely to be associated with the appearance of toxic effects than single doses over short periods of time. Additionally, the dose adjustment guided by therapeutic drug monitoring of individual patients has further enhanced the safety of these compounds (Prayle *et al.*, 2010; Beaucaire, 2000; Avent *et al.*, 2011).

Because of their beneficial traits and better knowledge of their less favorable properties, aminoglycosides are still widely used in the clinical settings for a variety of infections, especially infections caused by multidrug-resistant Gram-negative organisms. Gentamicin, tobramycin and amikacin are the most used aminoglycosides in the current clinical practice to fight urinary tract infections, peritonitis, sepsis cases or other infections caused by Enterobacteria (Krause *et al.*, 2016). Tobramycin has also shown good efficacy against respiratory tract infections caused by *P. aeruginosa* (Sawicki *et al.*, 2012). Neomycin is widely used for skin infections (Punjataewakupt *et al.*, 2019). Arbekacin, approved for its use only in Japan, is effective against infections produced by methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (Matsumoto, 2014). Amikacin, kanamycin and, most importantly, streptomycin are important components of tuberculosis and multidrug-resistant tuberculosis treatment (Brossier *et al.*, 2010). Streptomycin is also the drug of choice for the treatment of plague and tularemia, but its limited supply paired with the efficacy shown by gentamicin has made of the latter the primary therapeutic option nowadays (Boulanger *et al.* 2004; Mwengee *et al.* 2006; Snowden and Stovall, 2011).

3.- Aminoglycoside resistance

Shortly after the introduction of new aminoglycosides, resistant strains began to arise that produce enzymes capable of modifying the antibiotic molecule. The last decades of the 20th century posed a race between the appearance of novel bacterial resistance enzymes and strategies to overcome resistance, based on the discovery of new aminoglycoside molecules and the engineering of semi-synthetic derivatives that are not affected by the already existing resistance determinants. At the beginning of the 21st century the situation became more severe when a new horizontally acquired resistance mechanism based on the modification of the target-site entered the clinic. The addition of a methyl-group in aminoglycoside target residues of the 16S rRNA protects them from binding aminoglycoside molecules and, as a result, from their effects. The action of one of these 16S rRNA methyltransferases can block the binding of most of the clinically relevant aminoglycosides, jeopardizing the use of this class of antibiotics. This mechanism was already described as a chromosomally encoded self-defense strategy in environmental aminoglycoside-producing actinomycetes, but its dissemination alongside mobile genetic elements meant a shift in the combat approach against aminoglycoside resistance.

3.1.- Enzymatic drug modification

The first reports of aminoglycoside resistance mediated by modifying-enzymes date from the late 1960s (Ozanne *et al.*, 1969). Since then, many have been identified to date. These enzymes usually have limited substrates, which requires the coexistence of different complementary enzymes to completely abolish the efficacy of all the aminoglycosides employed in the clinic. These aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes alter their target aminoglycosides at –OH or –NH₂ groups by using either ATP or acetylCoA as co-substrates. The modified groups of the antibiotic molecule are usually essential for aminoglycoside binding to the ribosome. The enzymes are classified into three families:

the aminoglycoside *N*-acetyltransferases (AACs), the aminoglycoside *O*-phosphotransferases (APHs) and the aminoglycoside *O*-nucleotidyltransferases (ANTs). Some bacteria bear these genes in the chromosome, nevertheless, most of the genes encoding the enzymes are located on mobile genetic elements associated to other resistance determinants, thus facilitating their maintenance and spread. Further, due to the high number of enzymes and their continuous evolution, this mechanism is present among all clinically important bacterial species (Shaw *et al.*, 1993).

N-acetyltransferases catalyse the acetyl-CoA-dependent *N*-acetylation of one of the four amino groups of the 2-DOS aminoglycosides. The acetylation reduces the affinity of these compounds for their target in the 30S ribosomal subunit (Ramirez and Tomalsky, 2010). Enzymes belonging to this family are present in both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, and they generally show a very broad aminoglycoside resistance profile. AACs are divided into four classes, AAC(1), AAC(2'), AAC(3) and AAC(6'), based on the amino group that they modify. AAC(6') class is the most common of these enzymes, and can be extensively found in both Gram-positives and Gram-negative bacteria, on plasmids and chromosomes. There are two main subclasses of AAC(6') enzymes depending on their resistance profiles, AAC(6')-I and AAC(6')-II. A derivative of AAC(6')-Ib, AAC(6')-Ib-cr, shows additional resistance to fluoroquinolones and is considered to be a third subclass of AAC(6') enzymes by some authors (Robicsek *et al.*, 2006). Due to the large number of genes that belong to this class of enzymes, plus the absence of a unique nomenclature system, there have been several mistakes and difficulties when naming and classifying AAC(6') enzymes. Even though AAC(3)-IV does not belong to the most common class of aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes, it has gained attention lately because it includes apramycin in its broad substrate range and is considered the main apramycin resistance mechanism to date (Plattner *et al.*, 2020).

O-phosphotransferases catalyse the ATP-dependent phosphorylation of key hydroxyl substituents that are present on the aminoglycoside molecule. They are encoded by genes usually found on multidrug resistance plasmids and transposons among a wide range of bacterial pathogens. This family includes a large number of enzymes in Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, although they are more clinically relevant in Gram-positive pathogens (Vakulenko and Mobashery, 2003). These enzymes are divided in seven classes: APH(2''), APH(3'), APH(3''), APH(4), APH(6), APH(7'') and APH(9). Four of these classes, APH(4), APH(6), APH(7'') and APH(9), have no excessive clinical relevance (Ramirez and Tomalsky, 2010).

The third and last class of aminoglycoside inactivating enzymes is the one formed by the *O*-nucleotidyltransferases. They act by transferring an adenosine monophosphate group to hydroxyl groups of the aminoglycoside molecule. This class is comprised by the lowest number of enzymes and they can be divided in five classes of ANTs: ANT(2''), ANT(3''), ANT(4'), ANT(6), and ANT(9) (Ramirez and Tomalsky, 2010). ANT(2'') and ANT(3'') enzymes are often found in Gram-negative bacteria whereas ANT(4'), ANT(6), and ANT(9) tend to be harboured by Gram-positive pathogens (Shaw *et al.*, 1993). The genes coding for all these enzymes are often identified on mobile genetic elements. The most commonly found ANTs are the ANT(3'') enzymes. However, they are not considered the most clinically relevant enzymes of this group, as they are characterized by specifically conferring resistance to only streptomycin and spectinomycin (Hollingshead and Vapnek, 1985).

3.2.- 16S rRNA methyltransferases

Several 16S rRNA methyltransferases conferring aminoglycoside resistance have been described, mainly from different species of the genera *Streptomyces*, *Micromonospora*, and to a lesser extent, *Saccharopolyspora* (Demydchuk *et al.*, 1998; Kojic *et al.*, 1992; Ohta and Hasegawa, 1993). These methyltransferases are included in the *S*-adenosyl-L-methionine (SAM)-dependent RNA enzyme superfamily, and they protect the antibiotic-producing organisms of the toxic effect of their own products. They are classified in two groups based on their methylated target residue. The Kgm (kanamycin-gentamicin methyltransferases) family methylates residue G1405 whereas the Kam (kanamycin-apramycin methyltransferases) family methylates the A1408 residue (Husain *et al.*, 2011; Macmaster *et al.*, 2010; Savic *et al.*, 2009). Comparison of antibiotic resistance patterns between both families unambiguously identifies functional differences correlating with the modifications at G1405 and A1408. All Kgm family members methylate the position G1405 and confer high-level resistance to 4,6-DOS aminoglycosides due to the hydrogen bond formed between the residue and ring III of these aminoglycosides. Therefore, the addition of a methyl group at this position directly interferes with the binding of the antibiotic. However, the Kgm methyltransferases do not confer resistance to 4,5-DOS nor to other aminoglycosides such as apramycin and streptomycin, because rings III and IV are spatially located far from the position G1405. On the other hand, the Kam methyltransferases, that methylate the A1408 residue, confer high level resistance to neomycin, apramycin, kanamycin and, to a lesser extent, to gentamicin. Ring I, with a common structure among all the 2-DOS aminoglycosides, interacts with the residue A1408, which explains the resistance to this group of aminoglycosides.

In 2003, the first acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferase was reported (Galimand *et al.*, 2003). A *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated in 2000 from a urinary tract infection in France was found to be highly resistant to all 4,6-DOS aminoglycosides and fortimicin. The genetic determinant responsible for that phenotype was cloned into a laboratory *E. coli* strain revealing a protein with a 27% aminoacidic sequence similarity to a 16S rRNA methyltransferase from *Streptoalloteichus hindustanus*. This new protein was named ArmA for aminoglycoside resistance methyltransferase A. Only 4 months after the report of ArmA, another article describing a 16S rRNA methyltransferase in a Gram-negative bacterium was published (Yokoyama *et al.*, 2003). The 756 bp gene, designated *rmtA* (ribosomal RNA methyltransferase A), was identified in a *P. aeruginosa* strain isolated from a clinical sample in 1997 in Japan. This gene was found to confer high-level resistance to arbekacin, amikacin, gentamicin, kanamycin, and tobramycin when cloned and expressed in *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. The acquired methyltransferases RmtB and RmtC were subsequently discovered also in Japanese hospitals. The first one was isolated from a *Serratia marcescens* strain in 2002, and published in 2004 (Doi *et al.*, 2004). The resulting amino acid sequence of RmtB shared 82% identity with RmtA. The first identification of RmtC was published in 2006 (Wachino *et al.*, 2006). It was found in a *Proteus mirabilis* strain isolated in 2003, and it was also confirmed to be a 16S rRNA methyltransferase conferring the same resistance pattern as ArmA, RmtA, or RmtB. Successively, other 16S rRNA methyltransferases have been discovered among Gram-negative bacteria. RmtD was first reported in 2007 from a clinical *P. aeruginosa* strain in Brazil (Doi *et al.*, 2007a). RmtE methyltransferase was discovered in *E. coli* bovine isolates from the United States in 2010 (Davis *et al.*, 2010). RmtF was identified for the first time in a *K. pneumoniae* clinical strain in Reunion Island in 2012 (Galimand *et al.*, 2012), and RmtG and RmtH have been published in 2013 in *K. pneumoniae* isolates from Brazil and Iraq, respectively (Bueno *et al.*, 2013; O'Hara *et al.*, 2013). Recently, RmtI has been identified using functional metagenomics in human faecal samples in China (Wang *et al.*, 2022). All these methyltransferases have been confirmed to

methylate position G1405 and therefore present a resistance pattern similar to the Kgm family of intrinsic methyltransferases.

Acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases that modify position A1408 have also been discovered but so far only two enzymes of this group have been identified. The first one, NpmA, was reported in 2007 in a clinical *E. coli* strain from Japan (Wachino *et al.*, 2007). Many years later, in 2021, the second one, named NpmB, was found. This methyltransferase was observed in *E. coli* strains isolated in United Kingdom (Kawai *et al.*, 2021). Both acquired A1408 methyltransferases show an appropriate resistance phenotype according to the methylated residue, similar to the one of the Kam family.

In addition, variants of these acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases can be found. For instance, in 2011 in Argentina a gene was found bearing 9 aminoacidic substitutions compared to RmtD, which led to its classification as RmtD2 (Tijet *et al.*, 2011). RmtF, NpmA and NpmB also each have a variant that differs from the original sequence by just one amino acid (Tada *et al.*, 2017; Marsh *et al.*, 2019; Kawai *et al.*, 2021). Methyltransferases that have more than one variant are RmtB and RmtE, with a total of four and six variants, respectively (Costello *et al.*, 2019; Delgado-Blas *et al.*, 2023).

3.3.- Epidemiology and prevalence of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases

Although there was little data on the prevalence of aminoglycoside resistance mediated by 16S rRNA methylation in Gram-negative bacteria in the first years following their identification, available data has increased over the last years and a growing number of cases of resistance due to 16S rRNA methyltransferases has been reported worldwide. Information obtained from global or national antimicrobial surveillance studies is important to establish trends in antimicrobial resistance in bacteria. However, most of these surveillance programs focused on the analysis of the level of resistance to aminoglycosides rather than the underlying molecular mechanisms. For example, a study with isolates recovered from 70 hospitals of the United States of America between 2014 and 2015 under the ALERT Antimicrobial Surveillance Program revealed that commonly used aminoglycosides inhibited more than 90% of the Enterobacteria collected. However, when next-generation aminoglycosides were applied, more than a 99% of the isolates were susceptible (Castanheira *et al.*, 2018a). Since next-generation aminoglycosides are designed to overcome resistance conferred by modifying enzymes, this suggests that resistance to aminoglycosides in these collections may be largely mediated by AMEs. The prevalence of 16S rRNA methyltransferases on different continents has also been assessed. A further analysis with some of the ALERT program isolates showed that acquired methyltransferases were present in less than 0.1% of the studied isolates (Castanheira *et al.*, 2019). Another investigation that was carried out with isolates obtained in the CANWARD program from Canadian hospitals between 2013 and 2017, indicated a prevalence rate of 0.04% of 16S rRNA methyltransferases in this country (Walkty *et al.*, 2019). South America also presents very low rates of such methyltransferases as data from the WHONET-Argentina program exhibited (Tijet *et al.*, 2011). Information from European isolates of the ALERT program showed a prevalence of 1,4% of this resistance mechanism on isolates collected between 2014 and 2015 (Castanheira *et al.*, 2018b). In contrast, acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases seem to be most prevalent in Asian countries. Data from the SENTRY surveillance program from the years 2007 and 2008 indicated alarming prevalence rates of aminoglycoside resistance due to methylation among *Enterobacteriaceae* of 10.5% in India, 6.9% in China, 6.1% in Korea, 5% in Taiwan, and 3.1% in Hong Kong (Livermore *et al.*, 2011).

In addition to the information provided by global antimicrobial surveillance programs, a significant part of the gathered prevalence data comes from local studies. There are some reports generated at a local level from different hospitals and institutions worldwide and, regardless of the variability observed between centres, the trend observed in larger surveillance programmes is maintained. While prevalence rates around 1-1.5% are found in European countries (Sabtcheva et al., 2008; Galani et al., 2012; Piekarska et al., 2016), the highest prevalence is again found in Asian countries. Prevalence rates between 3% and 14% have been reported from China, Korea, or India (Kang et al., 2008; Yu et al., 2010; Hidalgo et al., 2013a; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Surprisingly, there are not as many reports from America as there are from Asia or Europe, and they are generally associated with non-fermentative Gram-negative bacilli, such as *A. baumannii* or *P. aeruginosa* (Doi et al., 2007b; Fontes et al., 2011). Furthermore, little information is available on the distribution of acquired methyltransferases in Africa. To date, only a few local reports have evaluated the presence of these resistance determinants in hospitals or regions from Algeria, Kenya, or Egypt. Overall, despite the disparity of the data, the prevalence rates observed in Africa are very low (Bouzidi et al., 2011; Naas et al., 2011; Zenati et al., 2017; Taitt et al., 2017).

When comparing the individual prevalence of the known acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases, evident differences in prevalence and global distribution can be observed. Hence, the ten known acquired methyltransferases can be divided into three groups according to their prevalence. In the first group we find ArmA and RmtB, the most prevalent methyltransferases so far and reported globally. RmtC and RmtF form part of the second group. They show less prevalence than ArmA or RmtB, but there has been a clear increase in the number of publications reporting RmtC worldwide in the last years, and although RmtF is one of the latest methyltransferases to be discovered, it seems to be spreading quickly worldwide. Finally, the third group is comprised by the very low prevalence and normally regionally confined methyltransferases. RmtD is the most prevalent methyltransferase belonging to this group and is mostly present in South America. Like RmtD, most reports from RmtG come from Brazil, but in a minor amount. RmtA has been mainly found in Asian countries, and a slight increase in reports has been seen recently. RmtE has been predominantly detected in the United States, while their variants seem to be localised in Asia and South America (Delgado-Blas et al., 2023). Just two reports are available from RmtH, which are both from Asia (O'Hara et al., 2013; Beyrouthy et al., 2017). NpmA has also been reported barely. It has been found in Japan, Saudi Arabia, China, and Iran (Wachino et al., 2007; Al Seikh et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2017; Sefidan et al., 2019), although some of these reports are not completely reliable. Nevertheless, a recent work describes the presence of *npmA* in the chromosomes of *Clostridium difficile* isolates from the United States, Canada, Australia, and the United Kingdom (Marsh et al., 2019). In the case of *npmB*, only two *E. coli* isolates of the United Kingdom are known to harbor this resistance gene (Kawai et al., 2021).

Acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases have mostly been identified in human strains isolated from either nosocomial or community-acquired infections. Nonetheless, the early detection of *armA* in a single *E. coli* isolated from a farm pig (Gonzalez-Zorn et al., 2005) raised the question of whether other sources such as animals, food products or the environment can be involved in the origin or spread of acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases. Some local studies have provided useful data describing the potential role as reservoirs that animals may play in the distribution of acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases. Nowadays, most of the 16S rRNA methyltransferases have been identified from

animals, except for RmtF, RmtG and RmtH. For instance, *ArmA* has been reported from pig isolates in Spain and South Korea (Gonzalez-Zorn *et al.*, 2005; Choi *et al.*, 2011), from cattle in South Korea (Choi *et al.*, 2011), and from chickens in China and South Korea (Choi *et al.*, 2011; Du *et al.*, 2012; Wang *et al.* 2017). Moreover, it has been also related with companion animals in China and Japan (Xia *et al.*, 2017; Maeyama *et al.*, 2018; Usui *et al.*, 2019), and it has been also found in *K. pneumoniae* ST11 isolated from dogs and cats in Spain (Hidalgo *et al.*, 2013b). This latter finding is noteworthy, as *K. pneumoniae* ST11 is a pathogenic clone adapted to humans and related to multidrug-resistant phenotypes. The low detection of this acquired methyltransferase among bacteria from pets led us to think that companion animals were not ultimately responsible for spreading this resistance determinant. However, the successful colonization of pets by a human-adapted clone, such as *K. pneumoniae* ST11, gives reason to consider companion animals as potential vectors for bacteria with high resistance to aminoglycosides. This might be promoted by the tight relationship between humans and pets, but also by using nearly the same aminoglycosides for the treatment of companion animals and humans.

RmtB is the 16S rRNA methyltransferase that shows the highest association with animals. In China, where RmtB has been reported the most, it is widely associated to pigs, chickens, and cattle, but has also been described in pets (Deng *et al.*, 2011a; Deng *et al.*, 2011b; Li *et al.*, 2012; Hou *et al.*, 2012; Xia *et al.*, 2017). In addition, a study performed in Japan showed that both dog and owner carried the same strain harbouring *rmtB*, which serves as strong evidence of the circulation between these two populations (Yao *et al.*, 2016). Finally, *rmtB* has also been reported in samples from cows in Europe (Lupo *et al.*, 2018). The prevalence of RmtB-producing bacteria from animals is in some cases much higher than from clinical strains. Moreover, around half of RmtB-positive isolates also harbour the fluoroquinolone resistance efflux pump QepA, and several studies have shown a link between both resistance determinants within the same mobile structure (Poirel *et al.*, 2012). Due to the excessive use of quinolones in animals in the last decades, this could promote a co-selection for RmtB and, in this particular case, animals would be the main transmission source.

Although RmtB is the most common methyltransferase in animals, other methyltransferases have also been reported in animals. RmtA was discovered recently on giant pandas in China (Zou *et al.*, 2018). RmtC has been described from chickens in China (Wang *et al.*, 2017). RmtD has been found in pigs and chickens in China (Wang *et al.*, 2017; Zhao *et al.*, 2018) and from migratory birds and a horse in Brazil (Leigue *et al.*, 2015; Martins *et al.*, 2018). The first description of RmtE was from *E. coli* recovered from cattle in the United States (Davis *et al.*, 2010) and was later also discovered in pigs from China (Xia *et al.*, 2015). NpmA has also been found in isolates from animal origin from Australia, the United States of America and Canada (Marsh *et al.*, 2019).

Apart from animals, 16S rRNA methyltransferases have also been encountered in environmental and food samples. For example, different studies have reported that the widespread dissemination of RmtB in China is not only associated with livestock and farm animals, but livestock-farming environments and farm workers (Yao *et al.*, 2011; Deng *et al.*, 2011a). In addition, enterobacteria harbouring *armA* and *rmtB* were found within the sewage disposal network from the city of Basel in Switzerland (Zurfluh *et al.*, 2017), and *rmtB* was also identified in a strain recovered from sewage of a hospital in China (Long *et al.*, 2019).

Furthermore, a study in Spain reported the presence of *armA* in wastewater from human and from animal origin (Colomer-Lluch *et al.*, 2014). The work aimed to characterize the resistome of the microbial population present in wastewater, which is not limited to the most common pathogens that are usually screened. The authors emphasize the role of non-culturable bacteria in maintaining resistance and provide more detailed information on the epidemiology and prevalence of 16S rRNA methyltransferases in that specific region.

RmtD was detected in a bacterium isolated from a Brazilian river (Fontes *et al.*, 2011) and RmtC was found in a sample from *S. enterica* collected from food in the United Kingdom (Hopkins *et al.*, 2010). Both strains were clonally related to human strains carrying the respective methyltransferase, indicating a clear link between the different sources of transmission and the impact on human health. Besides, an ArmA-producing *S. enterica* strain detected in Reunion Island was recovered from chicken meat sampled during a control by the retailer in a supermarket (Granier *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, no other multidrug resistant strain was detected from farm chickens during a surveillance study performed at that time in Reunion Island. This strongly suggests that these cases are the result of a cross contamination from a human origin, which still constitutes a major concern for the transmission of 16S rRNA methyltransferases.

4.- Next-generation aminoglycosides

The high levels of resistance we face today make the discovery of new antibiotics necessary. The discovery of the first aminoglycoside resistance strains via modifying enzymes led to first investigations for the development of new aminoglycoside compounds. The better understanding of the three-dimensional structure of the aminoglycosides, the modifying enzymes, and the interaction between them, pushed the design of different strategies to overcome resistance. Modification or elimination of the functional groups modified by the aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes is the most straightforward approach. Using this method, tobramycin and dibekacin were designed using kanamycin B as a template to prevent 3'-phosphorylation and, therefore, inactivation of these new aminoglycosides. Another way to block the activity of some aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes is to add methyl groups to the inactivation site of aminoglycosides, as in the case of some kanamycin B derivatives. However, this approach reduces the efficacy of the new molecule in comparison to the original antibiotic (Umezawa *et al.*, 1971; Matsumoto, 2014).

Modification of the 2-deoxystreptamine ring has been seen to reduce the activity of several aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes. Modification of the N-1 position of kanamycin yields amikacin, one of the most widely used aminoglycosides (Kagawuchi, 1972). The modification of the same position in dibekacin produces arbekacin. Arbekacin was only approved for use in Japan but, due to its potent activity against clinically important pathogens from both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and because amino glycoside-modifying enzymes have no effect on it, it has recently gained attention as a potential therapy for multidrug-resistant bacteria (Kondo *et al.*, 1973; Dube *et al.*, 2018; Clinical Trial NCT01659515).

Further modifications of the aminosugar ring were tested with promising results. A N-6', N-1, and N-3'' derivative using the naturally occurring aminoglycoside sisomicin as scaffold was obtained. The addition of these modifications gives resistance to all known aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes

except to AAC(2'). However, AAC(2') is a rarely encountered enzyme and has not been associated to mobile genetic elements, so its clinical importance is limited. In this novel compound, named ACHN-490 or plazomicin, the alterations introduced into the structure of sisomicin do not affect its natural potency. Plazomicin was approved by the FDA in June of 2018 for its use in complicated urinary tract infections caused by multidrug resistant enterobacteria and should be reserved for cases where no other treatment is available. Plazomicin use against carbapenem resistant enterobacteria has also been studied and, although not enough evidence was found in Phase III Clinical Trial to be approved for this purpose, enough information was gathered to recommend its "off-label" use as a last resort option. On the downside, plazomicin maintains the toxicity issues of the aminoglycoside class and, like the other 4,6-DOS derivatives, remains ineffective for those isolates bearing acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases. The fact that plazomicin is affected by preexisting resistance mechanisms limits its application and jeopardizes the development of new aminoglycoside compounds in this group (Wagenlehner *et al.*, 2019; Eljaaly *et al.*, 2019).

Despite not being affected by G1405 methyltransferases, 4,5-DOS semi-synthetic compounds have been reported to a much lesser extent, mostly due to a more complicated manipulation. Some neomycin derivatives resistant to several aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes, such as the bifunctional APH(2'')/AAC(6'), APH(3')-III or ANT(4')-I have been presented (Hanessian *et al.*, 2011). Recently, the novel paromomycin derivative propylamycin has been introduced, which does not only retain activity in the presence of diverse aminoglycoside resistance mechanisms, but also shows an increased ribosomal selectivity that leads to reduced toxic effects (Matsushita *et al.*, 2019).

Apramycin, which has been restricted to veterinary medicine since its discovery, has been shown to possess significantly lower toxic effects due to a lower activity against the mitochondrial ribosome (Matt *et al.*, 2013). Considering that G1405 methyltransferases are the only widespread 16S rRNA methyltransferases in the clinics so far and that they do not confer resistance to apramycin, this antibiotic and its derivatives could also be ideal candidates for bacteria that produce these methyltransferases. Recently, efforts have been made to bring apramycin to the human market. Therefore, an in-human Phase I clinical trial was conducted to evaluate its efficacy and safety and the results support further trials (Zhao *et al.*, 2022). In addition, selected modifications of apramycin structure give rise to compounds with enhanced potency (Lubriks *et al.*, 2022; Otsuka *et al.*, 2023). Despite these promising developments, 4,5-DOS and apramycin derivatives are not capable of overcoming resistance conferred by methylation of the A1408 residue. Although this mechanism is not yet widely spread, a potential outbreak threatens the application of these groups of aminoglycosides.

5.- Genomic study of antimicrobial resistance

The study of the genetic content of bacteria has advanced considerably in the last decades. From the discovery of Sanger sequencing methodology to the current different applications of whole genome sequencing, all progress made in the field has also enabled a breakthrough in the study of antimicrobial resistance.

Sanger sequencing, developed by Frederik Sanger in 1977, was one of the first methods that made the study of the genetic content of microorganisms possible. This technique, based on the activity of the DNA polymerase and the incorporation of labelled dideoxynucleotides, permits the accurate detection of the specific DNA sequence analysed (Sanger *et al.*, 1977). Nowadays, this approach is still largely used for the determination of the sequence of DNA fragments previously amplified via polymerase

chain reaction (PCR). The PCR method was developed by Kary Mullis in the decade of 1980s and allows the amplification of specific DNA fragments from complex templates and, therefore, the determination of the presence or absence of such fragments. However, to perform PCRs, the specific DNA target sequence must be known to design the oligonucleotides needed for amplification (Mullis *et al.*, 1986). The combination of both techniques is still widely used for the detection and identification of genes encoding antibiotic resistance mechanisms in bacteria (Anjum *et al.*, 2017). However, the limitation of this approach is that it can only be used to detect the resistance genes and mutations that have already been described (Ellington *et al.*, 2017).

The appearance of whole genome shotgun sequencing (WGS) in 1995 revolutionised the field completely. Based on breaking the bacterial genome into small fragments and the parallel sequencing of such fragments, this novel approach gave access to all the genetic information contained in a bacterium. Using WGS, a lot of information is generated in one sequencing run in a short amount of time with a very low error rate. This extensive information about the genomic content of bacteria has greatly improved the study of antimicrobial resistance. Today, not only the presence of known resistance genes can be assessed but genomes can be screened for the existence of novel resistance determinants. However, the increase in throughput came at expense of the sequence length. With this new technology, the sequenced fragments of the original DNA are of a few hundred base pairs in length, which makes it difficult to resolve the genetic organisation of the different genomic structures (Loman and Pallen, 2015).

The shortcomings of short read sequencing methods led to the development of a third generation of technologies, long read sequencing. The great length of the sequences generated allows the complete reconstruction of the organisation of the bacterial genome. Thanks to these sequencing technologies, the genetic context of antibiotic resistance genes can be completely evaluated and the association of resistance to different mobile genetic elements can be studied. Since the higher error rate of long read sequencing technologies does not allow the study of gene variations or point mutations (Koren and Phillippy, 2015), the information of both short- and long-read sequences can be combined. This hybrid method of long read data coupled with the high genetic resolution of short reads can generate closed genomes and plasmids with a low error rate (Lynch *et al.*, 2016).

In the last couple of years, the study of bacterial genomes has evolved from focusing on individual organisms to the analysis of complete microbial communities, which is called metagenomics. The term metagenomics was proposed in 1998 referred to the analysis of the collective genomes present in a certain environment (Handelsman *et al.*, 1998). Using a metagenomic approach to study bacterial communities, it becomes possible to virtually access the genetic content of all bacteria present, even the unculturable and unknown ones. In addition, metagenomics provides the opportunity to evaluate the functional potential of the whole community, including antimicrobial resistance.

A challenge in metagenomic studies can be to assign the resistance genes found to their host bacteria. Genome-resolved metagenomics offers the possibility to obtain drafted genomes from the bacteria present in the environment analysed, but sometimes these metagenome-assembled genomes (or MAGs) fall short in terms of completion due to the limitations of current bioinformatic tools. Furthermore, since the amount of data produced with the metagenomic approach is extremely high, genetic material from other bacteria can be easily introduced during the binning process, producing MAGs with some degree of 'contamination'. Taking this into account, minimum standards have been

set to produce high-quality MAGs that can raise the confidence of the assignment of resistance genes to bacteria observed with metagenomics (Bowers *et al.*, 2017). Nevertheless, this method also has its limitations. For example, MAGs from low abundant bacteria are not easily retrieved due to the lack of sequencing depth to produce enough data to draft their genomes.

Single cell genomics emerged as an alternative to overcome some of the disadvantages of genome-resolved metagenomics. The physical separation of the cells directly from environmental samples and the following sequencing and bioinformatic processing enable the analysis of the genomes of individual bacterial cells (Kaster and Sobol, 2020). Single cell genomics alone, as occurs with metagenomics, is also not a very effective technique for the analysis of low abundant bacteria. However, the combination of fluorescence-labelling of cells with targeted cell sorting has been proven an effective method for the study of individual genomes of low abundant bacteria (Dam *et al.*, 2020). This approach opens the door for the study of antimicrobial resistance genes in non-pathogenic bacteria present in low abundance in complex microbial communities.

Objectives

Antimicrobial resistance is a great threat to everything that has been achieved in the medical field. Since the discovery and development of new antibiotics is in clear regression, next-generation aminoglycosides have appeared as a strong alternative for combating bacterial infections in the next couple of years. However, the emergence and advance of resistance mechanisms to aminoglycosides, especially the 16S rRNA methyltransferases, jeopardize the application of old and new aminoglycosides. Even though the prevalence in pathogenic bacteria seems to be low in comparison with resistance determinants to first line antibiotics, some members of this family of resistance mechanisms have already been found worldwide and in very diverse origins. However, studies evaluating the prevalence of this resistance mechanism are scarce, and the role of non-pathogenic bacteria has not yet been assessed. Therefore, the main objective of the METAPRO PhD project is the application of a metagenomic approach for the study of the resistance determinants to next-generation aminoglycosides, with special interest in the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases in ecological niches from human, animal, and environmental origins. As part of this doctoral project, we aim to:

- Evaluate the prevalence of next-generation aminoglycoside resistance genes in the different ecological settings.
- Elucidate the bacterial and ecological reservoirs of resistance determinants to next generation aminoglycosides, with a special focus on the low abundant acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases.
- Predict the potential dissemination routes and describe the clones and mobile genetic elements that entail a major risk of aminoglycoside inefficacy.
- Analyse the effect of the use of antibiotics in the promotion of selection of next-generation aminoglycoside resistance genes.

We believe that the results obtained in the frame of this doctoral project can serve as the foundation of further research studies necessary to understand the propagation of next-generation aminoglycoside resistance mechanisms to be able to limit their spread. In addition, with the results obtained, we believe that in terms of commercialization and design of novel antibiotics of the aminoglycoside family, competent authorities will have more information to take the best decisions to promote and approve novel molecules to be released to the market.

4. *Materials and Methods*

Selection of Spanish shotgun metagenomic studies

The first goal of this work was the compilation of shotgun metagenomic projects conducted with Spanish samples to evaluate the prevalence of the different acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases in different human, animal, and environmental ecosystems. An extensive search was conducted in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) using different search strings to locate all the projects suitable for our analysis. In addition, a literature review of different metagenomic projects was also conducted to cross-check the results and extend the number of samples that could not be detected by string search in SRA.

Bioinformatic processing

The DNA sequences in FASTQ format of the different metagenomic samples were aligned against the ResFinder database using the *k*-mer based mapping tool KMA (v1.4.3) (Clausen *et al.*, 2018). Aminoglycoside resistance genes read counts were adjusted by gene length and abundance by calculating the “reads per kilo base per million mapped reads” (RPKM) values for each gene in the different samples using the formula:

$$\text{RPKM} = \frac{\text{Number of mapping reads}}{\left(\frac{\text{Gene length}}{1000}\right) * \left(\frac{\text{Total reads}}{10^6}\right)}$$

Microbial community taxonomic profiles for the diversity analysis were determined using Kraken 2 (2.1.2) (Wood *et al.*, 2019).

To confirm the presence of the different resistance genes of interest and analyse their close genetic context, assembly of the different samples was performed using MEGAHIT (v1.2.9) (Li *et al.*, 2015). Presence of resistance genes in the produced contigs was evaluated with abricate (v1.0.1). Contigs with the resistance genes studied were extracted and annotated with bakta (v1.7.0) (Schwengers *et al.*, 2021). Analysis of the sequences and comparative genomics were conducted with Geneious Prime software.

Binning of contigs in 16S rRNA containing samples was performed with metaBAT2, MaxBin2 and CONCOCT using METAWRAP pipeline (v1.3.2) (Uritskiy *et al.*, 2018). Completeness and contamination of the different bins was carried out with CheckM (v1.2.1) (Parks *et al.*, 2015). Refinement of the bins was performed using MDMcleaner (0.8.7) (Vollmers *et al.*, 2022).

Probe design

The 660 base pairs of the *npmA* gene were scanned to find suitable regions of 15 to 25 nucleotides to be used as probes with NCBI Primer Blast and Primer3Plus tools. To better improve signal intensity all the probes were designed on the complementary strand to not only target the corresponding DNA sequence but also hybridise to the potential messenger RNA that the *npmA*-harbouring bacteria might be producing. All the potential probes with appropriate GC content, melting temperatures and absence of secondary structures were subjected to a thermodynamic mathematical method to evaluate their hybridisation efficiency using mathFISH (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2011). Only probes with a hybridisation efficiency higher than 0.98 were further assessed. Finally, all the potential probes that passed the screening were evaluated via NCBI BLAST to check for the specificity of the probe to not label bacteria commonly present in the gut microbiome.

Cloning of FISH controls

To evaluate the efficiency of the probes, two control plasmids were produced. The *npmA* gene was amplified with *npmA_F* (5' – TTGTTAATACTCAAAGGAACAAAGACG – 3') and *npmA_R* (5' – TTAATGTTTTGAAACATGGCCAGA – 3') primers using *Taq* polymerase (Biotools) and the protocol recommended by the manufacturer. The *npmA* amplification product was subsequently introduced in pCR2.1 vector (Invitrogen) using TA cloning technology. In addition, a pCR2.1 vector was ligated without insert to be used as a negative control.

Fluorescent in situ hybridisation (FISH)

The protocol for fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH) is described in Haroon *et al.* (2013). Briefly, 1.5 ml of overnight culture were harvested at 10,000 x g for 2 minutes. Pellet was resuspended in 500 µl phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and centrifuged again for 2 minutes at 10,000 x g and the supernatant discarded. All further steps were performed in the dark to prevent photobleaching of the probe. For hybridisation, pellet was resuspended in 45 µl of hybridisation buffer and 1 µl of the probe at the proper concentration was added to the mixture. Samples were incubated at 46°C for 3 hours in a water bath. After incubation, samples were centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 2 minutes and pellet was washed with 500 µl pre-warmed washing buffer. Sample was centrifuged again at 10,000 x g for 2 minutes and resuspended in 500 µl of washing buffer and incubated at 48°C for 2 minutes in a water bath. After incubation, samples were centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 2 minutes and pellet was resuspended in 500 µl ice-cold PBS. Finally, samples were centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 2 minutes and pellet was resuspended in 500 µl ice-cold PBS and stored at 4°C for further analysis. All solutions used for FISH are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of solutions used for fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH).

Buffer	Components	Quantity
Hybridisation buffer	ddH ₂ O	998 µl
	Tris-HCl 1M	40 µl
	NaCl 5M	360 µl
	Formamide	600 µl
	SDS 10%	2 µl

Washing buffer

ddH ₂ O	11870 µl
Tris-HCl 1M	250 µl
NaCl 5M	255 µl
EDTA 0.5M	125 µl
SDS 10%	12.5 µl

An ethanol dehydration step was added to the protocol to enhance probe hybridisation efficiency. Before hybridisation, pellet was washed with 500 µl of increasing concentrations of ethanol (50%, 80% and 98%) and incubated 3 minutes at room temperature prior centrifugation at 10,000 x g for 2 minutes. After dehydration steps, hybridisation was carried out as described before.

Fluorescence microscopy

Microscopic images were taken with an inverse ZEISS Axio Observer Microscope (Carl Zeiss AG). After hybridisation with the corresponding probe, 4 µl of each sample was placed on a microscopic slide with a cover slip on top and directly visualised at 100x magnification using Immersol 518F (Carl Zeiss AG) as immersion oil.

Fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS)

A BD FACSMelody cell sorter (Becton-Dickson) equipped with a 100 µm nozzle was used to evaluate the efficiency of staining of our probes with the FISH protocol applied. A 1:100 dilution of the FISH preparations in PBS was excited with a 488 nm laser to obtain forward (FSC) and side scatter (SSC) of single cells, and, additionally, a 660/10 nm filter was used to detect the fluorescence of each cell. Gates were produced with a positive and a negative control to evaluate the percentage of cells positively stained with the different probes and probe concentrations.

Diversity analysis

Shannon index was calculated for all the samples to estimate their individual richness. Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index was also calculated to assess the similarity in the composition of the different samples. Both these indexes were calculated using the vegan R package.

Differential abundance analysis was calculated using Linear discriminant analysis of the effect size (LEfSe) algorithm (<https://huttenhower.sph.harvard.edu/galaxy/>).

5. Scientific Results and Discussion

Chapter 1: Acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases in Spain

Metagenomic sample selection

In our search, a total of 884 Spanish metagenomic samples from 13 different project were found in the SRA database with the parameters used. As expected, most of the samples have human origin, 816, but animal and environmental origins are also covered in this dataset. Pig with 28 samples and poultry with 20 samples are the only animal origins found, and wastewater with 13 samples, freshwater with 5 and soil with 2 are the environmental origins detected in our screening (Table 2).

Table 2. Metagenomic samples in the databases included in our study.

Bioproject	Number of samples	Origin
PRJEB33098	9	Human
PRJEB3227	7	Human
PRJEB27799	12	Human
PRJEB14215	32	Human
PRJEB1220	756	Human
PRJNA371649	8	Pig
PRJEB22062	40	Pig and poultry
PRJEB13831	6	Wastewater
PRJEB27054	6	Wastewater
PRJEB23496	1	Wastewater
PRJNA342151	3	Freshwater
PRJNA238866	2	Freshwater
PRJNA318875	2	Soil

Prevalence and abundance of acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases in metagenomic samples

All the samples were screened mapping the reads of the different metagenomic samples to the Resfinder database to see if they contain any acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferase. Of the 884 samples surveyed, 61 of them presented one or more methyltransferases. In terms of origin, no 16S rRNA methyltransferases were detected in environmental samples. However, a 3.1% of human samples, a 15.4% of wastewater samples, a 50% of poultry samples and an 85.7% of the pig samples showed the presence of methyltransferases. The enzymes detected is *rmtD*, *rmtF*, *rmtG*, *rmtH* and *npmA*. *rmtF* is the most prevalent, been found in 33 samples, closely followed by *npmA*, present in 26 samples. If we break it down per sample type, *rmtD* is the most prevalent methyltransferase in humans, being detected in 10 samples, followed by *rmtF* and *npmA*, present in 8 samples each, and *rmtH*, in 3. In pig samples, 23 out of the 28 samples investigated showed the presence of *rmtF*, and 8 out of the 28 presented *npmA*. Interestingly, *rmtG* and *rmtD* were also detected in pig samples once and twice respectively. In poultry samples the only methyltransferase detected was *npmA*, present in half of the metagenomes analysed. Finally, in wastewater only *rmtF* was found in 2 out of the 13 samples investigated (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases by sample type.

The relative abundance of the different genes in the different environments was evaluated in reads per kilo base per million mapped reads (RPKM). In general, the relative abundance of all the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases was low. Most of the samples with independence of the resistance gene detected or the origin show RPKM values between 0.1 and 1. The highest abundance values are observed in *npmA*, that show a peak of abundance in 16.5 RPKM. However, in some samples it is also detected a very low relative abundance (0.08 RPKM). Similar values are shown by *rmtD2* in two human samples (4.67 and 8.12 RPKM), but since are the two projects with the less amount of reads the abundance can be overestimated. Again, in some samples *rmtD2* is barely detected, with a 0.05 RPKM value (Table 3).

Table 3. Relative abundance (in RPKM) of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases detected.

Gene		Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
<i>npmA</i>	Human	0.76	0.83	0.42	0.10	1.36
	Pig	0.21	0.18	0.14	0.08	0.54
	Poultry	5.32	4.60	4.88	0.13	16.52
	TOTAL	2.35	0.68	3.80	0.08	16.52
<i>rmtD2</i>	Human	1.63	0.57	2.65	0.05	8.12
	Pig	0.12	0.12	-	0.12	0.12
	TOTAL	1.49	0.57	2.56	0.05	8.12
<i>rmtF</i>	Human	1.17	1.01	0.88	0.16	2.80
	Pig	0.98	0.92	0.54	0.39	2.41
	Wastewater	0.08	0.08	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.08	0.08
	TOTAL	0.97	0.83	0.66	0.08	2.80
<i>rmtH</i>		0.15	0.18	0.09	0.05	0.22
<i>rmtG</i>		0.10	0.10	-	0.10	0.10

Nevertheless, differences in the abundance per origin of the sample can be detected for some of the methyltransferases. For example, *npmA* in humans and pigs show a similar abundance, but in poultry is much higher (Tukey HSD, $p < 0.01$). On the other hand, *rmtF* levels in humans and pigs show a similar

trend, while in wastewater is lower, but no statistical difference can be detected (ANOVA, $p=0.192$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Relative abundance of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases *npmA* and *rmtF* by sample type.

Genetic context of acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases in metagenomic samples

Since mapping approaches are known for the high possibility of false positives, confirmation of the presence of the 16S rRNA methyltransferases was attempted with an assembly approach. Due to the low abundance of the methyltransferases detected, *rmtD*, *rmtF*, *rmtG* and *rmtH* were not detected in any of the assemblies. On the other hand, *npmA* was assembled in a contig in 9 out of the 26 samples where the gene was detected by the mapping approach. All the contigs correspond to poultry samples. The *npmA* gene, corresponding to the *npmA1* variant, can be detected in two different genetic contexts (Figure 2). The first genetic environment present high nucleotidic identity with the original context where the gene was firstly described in 2007, as well as with the pTRACA22 plasmid, a plasmid that has not been linked to any bacterial species yet. However, all the open reading frames (ORFs) surrounding *npmA* in these contigs have more than a 90 percent of identity at the protein level with different bacteria from the order Eubacteriales. The second environment found is completely new and presents as well high-level identity at a nucleotidic level with different genera from the Eubacteriales order. At a protein level, most of the ORFs have more than 99 percent of identity with proteins from *Clostridioides difficile* (Figure 2).

Figure 3. Close genetic context of *npmA* in the contigs assembled from shotgun metagenomic samples.

Further, we wanted to see to what extent these genetic contexts can be associated with a plasmid. Based on the results of the machine learning classifier PlasX, the first environment has a high probability of being of plasmidic origin (0.96), while the second one is most likely not a plasmid (0.04). These results correlate with the ORF study, as in the first context we can see functions normally associated with plasmids, like toxin-antitoxin systems or a plasmid recombination enzyme, as well as being detected this similar context in the unknown plasmid pTRACA22 of the human gut microbiome. On the other hand, the second context observed present a relaxase, which could suggest a plasmidic origin. However, the rest of the ORFs seem to form part of the normal chromosome of different Eubacteriales.

Binning of the contigs containing *npmA* was performed with three different binning tools. 16 different bins from 6 of the *npmA* positive samples were produced. Except for one, all the bins were highly incomplete, highly contaminated or both (Table 4). However, running a cleaning tool on the bins removed the *npmA* contigs from them, as they may have been included incorrectly.

Table 4. CheckM results of the bins containing *npmA* contigs.

Sample	Binning tool	Bin	Completeness	Contamination
ERR2241748	MAXBIN2	Bin 13	82.52	21.99
ERR2241749	CONCOCT	Bin 87	87.07	131.91
	MAXBIN2	Bin 39	75.65	37.01
	METABAT2	Bin 32	62.07	1.72
ERR2241750	CONCOCT	Bin 102	14.80	0.32
	MAXBIN2	Bin 22	97.23	41.44
ERR2241753	CONCOCT	Bin 34	8.77	0.00
	MAXBIN2	Bin 42	98.68	14.75
ERR2241754	CONCOCT	Bin 33	32.68	2.55
	MAXBIN2	Bin 57	41.87	18.86
ERR2241755	CONCOCT	Bin 145	96.93	3.82
	MAXBIN2	Bin 17	70.69	33.86

Targeted metagenomics of antimicrobial resistance genes

Targeted metagenomics allow for the identification of specific genes in a complex metagenome background. A sequencing capture platform for antimicrobial resistance genes has already been designed and implemented in the project PRJNA371649 (Lanza *et al.*, 2018), that forms part of the

dataset of the present study. The same 8 pig faecal samples were analysed both by conventional shotgun metagenomics and using this targeted metagenomics method. Interestingly, when with conventional metagenomics only half of the samples presented an acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferase, after the application of the capturing platform all samples presented both *rmtF* and *npmA*. In addition, 5 samples harboured *rmtG* and 2 samples presented *rmtD*.

From the assembly approach we were able to retrieve three out of the four methyltransferases but not in all the samples that contained them. Thanks to the capturing of more reads, *npmA* was assembled in all the samples, but only in 6 of them the gene was complete, as one contig was falling short and in other the *npmA* gene was interrupted. In four of the contigs the *npmA2* variant was found, while two of them showed a potential novel *npmA* variant not found to date. In this new variant, the C124T nucleotidic mutation with respect to both *npmA1* and *npmA2* produce an aminoacidic change of a leucine for a phenylalanine at position 42. In addition, the *npmA3* variant also shows the same mutations in positions 330, 393 and 450 that *npmA2* presents against *npmA1*. All six contigs with the gene complete show a similar genetic environment, that differs completely from the genetic contexts where *npmA1* and *npmA2* have been found so far, as well as the genetic context of *npmA* in poultry. The *npmA* gene seems to be also associated with an *IS30* like the *npmA2* gene, but in our case, it seems that is from the same family but it is not the same insertion sequence (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Close genetic context of *npmA* in the original context of NpmA2 and from the contigs assembled from targeted metagenomic samples.

With the same approach, *rmtF* was assembled in 7 out of the 8 samples, but 3 of them did not cover the whole length of the gene. The other 4 present various polymorphisms with respect to *rmtF1* and *rmtF2*. All of them present the A193G characteristic of *rmtF2* in comparison to *rmtF1*, and up to 23 different positions are mutated in the 4 *rmtF* genes, presenting all different mutation profiles. These mutations lead to aminoacidic changes that make our finding to be potentially considered as 4 new *rmtF* variants. The list of variants and the aminoacidic changes are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. Novel variants of *rmtF* and their aminoacidic changes.

Variant	Aminoacid change(s)	Reference
<i>rmtF2</i>	K65E	Tada <i>et al.</i> , 2017
<i>rmtF3</i>	K65D	This work
<i>rmtF4</i>	M31T, K65D	This work
<i>rmtF5</i>	M31T, K65D, V248M	This work
<i>rmtF6</i>	T49A, K65E, A72S, D238N	This work

In the contigs produced, only two were long enough to detect an ORF flanking *rmtF* in its upstream region. This upstream ORF present high nucleotidic identity with regions found in uncultured bacteria from human, and a protein level has high identity with a tRNA-guanine transglycosylase related to Clostridiales bacteria.

The low abundant 16S rRNA methyltransferase *rmtG* was also assembled in one of the samples. The *rmtG* recovered presented 25 polymorphisms with respect to the canonical *rmtG* sequence reported. All the nucleotidic changes produce 11 aminocidic modifications (95.8% protein identity with RmtG), that is at the border of been cosidered a new methyltransferase. In the *rmtG* contig there is not much information about the genetic context where the gene is located (46 base pairs upstream and 293 base pairs downstream), but it seems to be already detected in uncultured bacteria from human habitats.

Chapter 2: Global study of *npmA*

Acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases seem to be more prevalent that the global genomic studies tell mainly due to its maintenance in non-pathogenic bacteria in the gut microbiome of humans and different animal species. It is especially worrisome the case of *npmA*, a low abundant methyltransferase with the widest range of aminoglycoside resistance. In our Spanish dataset it appears to be part of the gut microbiome of humans, pigs, and chickens, but the exact bacterial reservoir in the different environments is still not known. However, thanks to the great effort performed by other research groups, we had access to a major screening of antimicrobial resistance genes in shotgun metagenomic samples (Martiny *et al.*, 2022).

Prevalence of *npmA* in metagenomics projects

In the 214095 sequencing runs analysed, the *npmA* gene was detected in 1437 of them (a 0.67 percent). If we break down the samples by origin, we see that, as expected from our previous results, most of the samples (94.50 percent) come from human, poultry, and pig origins, with 657, 385 and 316 positive runs respectively. Interestingly, *npmA* was detected in other animal sources, like cow (10 samples) or deer (4 samples), but also in environmental samples from wastewater (8) or air origin (14) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. (A) Abundance of *npmA* positive samples per source. (B) Close-up of low abundant sources of *npmA*.

If we analyse the percentage of projects positive *npmA* from the total number of sequencing runs analysed, we confirmed the observations seen in the Spanish dataset. Less than a 1 percent of the human samples were *npmA* positive, but the prevalence of *npmA* in pig and poultry origins is way higher, being a 9.70 and 26 percent respectively.

Global distribution of *npmA*

If we divide the *npmA* positive samples per country of origin, we can observe that this 16S rRNA methyltransferase is globally spread. The *npmA* methyltransferase can be detected from all the continents except from South America, but the low number of metagenomic projects of these countries might have contributed to this result. The country with most positive samples is China with 54.49 percent of the *npmA* positive projects, followed by Australia with a 15.52 percent and by United States with 6.54 percent of all the samples. In Europe, the country with a greater number of samples is Germany, with the 3.34 percent of the samples, followed by France with 2.60 percent and Spain with 1.81 percent of the positive samples (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Global distribution of *npmA* positive metagenomic samples.

Assembly approach of *npmA* positive samples

The mapping approach of the *npmA* positive samples was followed by an assembly-based analysis. Due to limited computational capacity, we selected only those samples that through mapping showed that the *npmA* gene was completely covered. Using this filter, our dataset was reduced to 378 samples. From the assembly of these 378 samples, 350 contigs containing *npmA* were produced. The 350 *npmA* positive contigs come from different sources and different countries (Figure 7). As expected, most of the contigs come from Chinese samples, but other 12 countries from different continents are also represented. In terms of source of the samples, poultry, human and swine origins are the most represented, but also 2 contigs from hospital surfaces and 1 from cattle form part of the dataset.

Figure 7. Distribution of the *npmA* contigs by (A) source and (B) country.

We extracted the *npmA* gene from the 350 contigs produced to evaluate the genetic variants more prevalent in the world. The variant most represented is *npmA1*, encountered a total of 291 times (an 83.14 percent of the samples). The *npmA2* variant was only detected in 3 samples (a 0.86 percent). Interestingly, 15 samples presented different polymorphisms in the *npmA* gene unknown, being potentially novel variants of the gene. In the end, only 11 *npmA* genes presented aminoacidic substitutions, resulting in the description of 6 potential novel variants, named *npmA4* to *npmA9* (Table 6).

Table 6. Novel variants of *npmA* and their aminoacidic changes.

Variant	Aminoacid change(s)	Reference
<i>npmA2</i>	K131N	Marsh <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>npmA3</i>	L42F, K131N	This work
<i>npmA4</i>	K131N, A198T	This work
<i>npmA5</i>	K131N, L157I	This work
<i>npmA6</i>	S2L	This work
<i>npmA7</i>	H134Y	This work
<i>npmA8</i>	T151K	This work
<i>npmA9</i>	A133G	This work

Several residues of *npmA* have been marked as essential for the aminoglycoside resistance function in the literature (Husain *et al.*, 2011; Dunkle *et al.*, 2014). Interestingly, these critical residues are maintained in all the new variants found from metagenomic samples and, therefore, they should maintain the methylation of the A1408 of the 16S rRNA methyltransferase and the resistance spectra (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Alignment of amino acid sequences of all the *npmA* variants. In red are marked the amino acid changes. Grey boxes indicate the critical residues for NpmA1 function.

Chapter 3: Single cell genomics for the detection of NpmA reservoirs

Based on the results obtained in the first chapter of this report, we estimated that the abundance of the reservoirs of the *npmA* resistance gene is in the limit of the detection and, since it is frequently associated to mobile genetic elements, conventional metagenomic analysis fall short to identify the bacteria that contribute to its maintenance in the gut metagenome. Here we describe a method that combines fluorescence labelling of the resistance gene with fluorescence activated cell sorting for the isolation and sequencing of single cells harbouring the *npmA* gene.

Probe design

Following the selection criteria proposed (see Materials and Methods section), three probes with the most appropriate characteristics were selected for fluorescence in situ hybridisation of the *npmA* gene. Probes with a length of less than 20 base pairs were discarded because of high levels of hybridisation to different bacterial species commonly found in the gut microbiome. A threshold of 80 percent or less of homology was set to ensure that unspecific binding to other bacterial targets can be avoided. The probes were selected to have different unspecific binding profiles and to be separated at least 50 base pairs from each other to cover different topological positions in the gene. The red fluorescent dye

Atto647N was attached to the 5' end of the probes. The full characteristics of the three selected probes are listed in Table 7.

Table 7. Characteristics of the *npmA* probes selected for this study.

Name	Position	Sequence	%GC	Tm	He	Secondary structure	BLAST hits
npmA_P1	79-101	5'-CCAGTACCCAAATCTATATGCAC-3'	43.4	56.8°C	0.9996	None	<i>Clostridioides difficile</i> – 69%
npmA_P2	427-447	5'-TTCCGCTTCTTCGTATGAATC-3'	42.8	56.2°C	1.0000	Very weak	<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i> – 76%
npmA_P3	520-540	5'-ATCAATGCGAAAACCTGAGTT-3'	38	56.4°C	0.9826	Very weak	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i> – 76% <i>Bacteroides</i> spp. – 76%

Fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH)

To evaluate whether the *in silico* designed probes perform as expected and are suitable for the detection of *npmA* bacterial reservoirs, the resistance gene was inserted in the pCR2.1 plasmid (Figure 9). pCR2.1 plasmid has a pBR322 origin of replication, that makes it have around 20 to 40 copies per cell. Both pCR2.1 and pCR2.1::*npmA* were introduced in *Escherichia coli* K-12 to be used as negative and positive control of probe hybridisation, respectively.

Figure 9. Map of the *npmA* control plasmid pCR2.1::*npmA*.

Microscopic visualisation after application of a conventional FISH protocol with 2.5 ng/ μ l of probe npmA_P1 to an overnight culture of positive and negative control strains (see Materials and Methods) revealed that a very low proportion of cells stained (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Microscopic image of *E. coli* K-12 with pCR2.1::*npmA* plasmid after application of FISH protocol with 8 ng/ μ l of npmA_P1 probe.

Applying an ethanol dehydration step has been reported to enhance the hybridisation of the probes. Results of hybridisation of 2.5 ng/ μ l of probe npmA_P1 after the ethanol dehydration step showed that more than an 80 percent of the cells in the positive control stained, while no cells stained in the negative control. Increasing npmA_P1 probe concentration to 8 ng/ μ l improved Atto647N signal, but a similar proportion of cells were stained as with lower concentration (Figure 11). Nevertheless, the signal intensity varies between cells and sometimes the inclusion of a cell as stained or unstained is subjective.

Figure 11. Microscopic image of *E. coli* K-12 with pCR2.1::*npmA* plasmid after ethanol dehydration and application of FISH protocol with 8 ng/ μ l of npmA_P1 probe.

Probe npmA_P2 was also evaluated with ethanol dehydration and different probe concentrations (ranging from 2.5 to 15 ng/ μ l). Again, around 80 to 90 percent of the cells positively stained while in the negative control none of them did (Figure 12). On the other hand, with independence of the npmA_P3 probe concentrations tested, no fluorescent signal was captured for any of the cells in the positive control with this FISH protocol.

Figure 12. Microscopic image of *E. coli* K-12 with pCR2.1::*npmA* plasmid after ethanol dehydration and application of FISH protocol with 15 ng/ μ l of npmA_P2 probe.

In addition, combination of npmA_P1 (8 ng/ μ l) and npmA_P2 (15 ng/ μ l) was evaluated to see the performance in terms of signal intensity and percentage of cells stained. Surprisingly, in the visual observation of the microscopic images, a slightly lower proportion of cells stained (around 72 percent of cells) (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Microscopic image of *E. coli* K-12 with pCR2.1::*npmA* plasmid after ethanol dehydration and application of FISH protocol with 8 ng/ μ l of *npmA_P1* probe and 15 ng/ μ l of *npmA_P2* probe.

Fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS)

Hybridisation efficiency of probes *npmA_P1* and *npmA_P2* was further analysed via combination of FISH with fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS). First, the negative control was analysed to set the gates for population and negative fluorescence in the corresponding scattergrams (Figure 15A and 15C). The study of the positive control followed and based on the gates proposed by our negative control, we can clearly define a subpopulation of cells distinctively marked with the red fluorescence provided by Atto647N dye that can be gated and sorted out for further analysis (Figure 15D). If we focus on the numbers, we see that a 46.26 percent of the cells can be sorted giving margin to avoid potential false positives. This same experiment was performed with mock communities with different ratios of negative and positive cells (50:50 and 90:10) to test whether this method is capable of detect *npmA* positive cells even when the abundance is low. The results confirmed what we saw with the positive control alone, being detected around one cell every two as positive to *npmA*, as a 26.08 and a 5.20 percent of cells are detected in the positive gate.

Figure 15. Results from the fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS) using *npmA_P1* probe. (A) Scattergram of SSC vs FSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1, (B) scattergram of SSC vs FSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1::*npmA*, (C) scattergram of Atto647N vs SSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1, (D) scattergram of Atto647N vs SSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1::*npmA*, (E) number and percentage of events in the different gates for *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1 and, (F) number and percentage of events in the different gates for *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1::*npmA*.

Same methodology was used to evaluate the performance of *npmA_P2* probe (Figure 16). Interestingly, *npmA_P2* probe seems to work slightly better than *npmA_P1*, as it detects almost a 4 percent more of cells as positive to *npmA* leaving also margin to avoid potential false positives. In the mock communities, this better performance is not maintained. A 23.38 percent of cells can be sorted in the positive gate in the 50:50 mixture, while only a 3.56 percent of the events could be sorted from the 90:10 community.

Figure 16. Results from the fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS) using npmA_P2 probe. (A) Scattergram of SSC vs FSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1, (B) scattergram of SSC vs FSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1::npmA, (C) scattergram of Atto647N vs SSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1, (D) scattergram of Atto647N vs SSC of *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1::npmA, (E) number and percentage of events in the different gates for *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1 and, (F) number and percentage of events in the different gates for *E. coli K-12* with pCR2.1::npmA.

Chapter 4: Effect of apramycin use in the selection of apramycin resistance genes in poultry

Sample selection and apramycin use

In the present study we used a metagenomic sequencing analysis of the gut microbiome of poultry to analyse the effects that the use of apramycin has on the microbiome composition. For that purpose, we included the analysis of twenty Spanish poultry farms with antibiotic use known collected within the EFFORT project. The twenty sampled farms were divided into two groups based on apramycin use: a treatment group comprised by seven farms that used apramycin at the time of sampling and a control group that did not use apramycin during that time.

Alpha-diversity analysis of poultry gut microbiome composition

To assess whether apramycin use has any effect on the gut microbiome composition the Shannon-Wiener diversity index was calculated for bacterial composition and antimicrobial resistance gene content from every sample individually. When grouping samples per treatment group we observe that there is no statistical significance difference in terms of bacterial composition between groups (Mann-Whitney U test, $p=0.757$) (Figure 17A). On the other hand, when looking into the diversity of resistance genes in the different farms we observe that those that used apramycin exhibit a higher diversity (Mann-Whitney U test, $p=0.024$) (Figure 17B).

Figure 17. Alpha-diversity analysis using Shannon-Wiener index from (A) bacterial composition and (B) antimicrobial resistance gene content of the poultry farms grouped by treatment.

Beta-diversity analysis of poultry gut microbiome composition

To further assess whether apramycin use reshapes the contents of the gut microbiota, the similarity of the bacterial and resistance genes composition of all the samples was compared through the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index. Plotting the distances between the different bacterial compositions in a Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) shows that all the samples tend to cluster together with

independence of the treatment group (Figure 18A). This observation is further confirmed by the statistical analysis performed directly on the distances between samples (PERMANOVA, $p=0.271$). In terms of antimicrobial resistance gene content, using the same methodology, this time a more evident clusterisation based on the treatment group can be observed (Figure 18B), being again the statistics confirming the observations (PERMANOVA, $p=0.037$).

Figure 18. Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) of the distance in (A) bacterial composition and (B) antimicrobial resistance gene content calculated with the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index.

Differential abundance analysis of antimicrobial resistance genes between treatment groups

Diversity analysis carried out exhibited that apramycin use increases the diversity of antimicrobial resistance genes without having a major effect on the taxonomic composition of the poultry gut microbiome. To determine which features are the main contributors to the differences observed in the antimicrobial resistance gene composition, a Linear discriminant analysis of the Effect Size (LEfSe) was performed (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Linear discriminant analysis of the Effect Size (LEfSe) of the antimicrobial resistance gene content.

Resistance genes to aminoglycosides (*aph(4)-Ia*, *aph(6)-Id*, *aac(3)-IV*, *aph(3'')-Ib*, *ant(4')-Ib*, *ant(9)-Ia*, *npmA*, *str1*), to chloramphenicol (*cmx*), to betalactams (*bleO*) and to tetracycline (*tet(O/W)2*) are more abundantly found in the farms that used apramycin, while only tetracycline resistance genes *tet(O/W)5*, *tet(O/W)1* and *tetK* are more frequently found in the control group. Interestingly, many resistance genes to aminoglycosides were more abundant in the apramycin group, but only *aac(3)-IV* and *npmA* are known to confer resistance to apramycin.

Based on these results, we looked for the presence of the two apramycin resistance genes and their relative abundance in the different samples. *aac(3)-IV* gene was detected in all the sample with independence of the treatment group, with abundances ranging from 9.95 to 137.14 RPKM (median 77.41 RPKM) in the farms that used apramycin, and abundances of 0.17 to 116.43 RPKM (median 0.59 RPKM) in the control farms. In contrast, *npmA* does not appear as abundant as *aac(3)-IV*. *npmA* was detected in all the farms that used apramycin (with abundance ranging from 1.35 to 16.52 RPKM, median 5.08 RPKM), while it was only detected in three out of the thirteen control farms sampled (with abundances of 0.54, 4,82 and 0.13 RPKM).

Since *npmA* has been largely studied in the previous chapter of this report, here we decided to focus our study on *aac(3)-IV* resistance gene.

Genetic environment of apramycin resistance genes

To understand how the apramycin resistance genes became more abundant after apramycin use, an assembly-based approach was used to know the close genetic context of the genes. In the assemblies performed from all the samples, *aac(3)-IV* gene was recovered from sixteen out of the twenty farms sampled, while *npmA* gene was recovered only in nine of them. Length of *aac(3)-IV* contigs range from 2528 to 10505 base pairs (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Close genetic context of the *aac(3)-IV* gene in the contigs obtained from the assembly of the shotgun metagenomic data.

The close genetic context of this gene reveals a high association with other aminoglycoside resistance gene, *aph(4)-Ia*, an insertion sequence, *ISEc59*, and a truncated form of a Tn3-family transposase, as in all the contigs obtained these four genes were found together. Four of the contigs were long enough to show the genetic context where this association unit is embedded, showing that it can be found in very different environments. It seems that different insertion sequences can facilitate the mobilisation of the association unit, as an IS26 and an ISL3 family transposase, as well as truncated forms of an IS6100 and an IS5564 are found in the near context. ISL3 is commonly found in different families of the Micrococcales order, IS5564 in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, Micrococcales, as well as different species of *Corynebacterium*, and IS26 and IS6100 are highly associated to plasmids belonging to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, suggesting that they could be actively mobilising the unit between different bacterial species in the gut microbiome. In addition, the rest of open reading frames present in the contigs confirm the different origins of the *aac(3)-IV* gene. The partial CDS of a recombinase found flanking the IS26 is identical to one found in different *Enterobacteriaceae* plasmids, and the two CDSs encoding a stress protein and a transporter associated to the truncated form of IS5564 show high identity nucleotidic levels with different Micrococcales species.

Global distribution of *aac(3)-IV*

Since *aac(3)-IV* seems to be highly prevalent in chicken farms, we wanted to evaluate the overall prevalence of *aac(3)-IV* in the world. To do that, we used the NCBI NDARO database (Accessed September 2022) as our reference. At the date of consultation, the NDARO database presented 17809 organisms carrying *aac(3)-IV* out of the 1188814 total organisms included (a 1.19 percent of the organisms). From all the positive isolates, a 99.8 percent correspond to different species from the Enterobacteriaceae family. Based on the origin of the sample where the isolate was obtained, we observe that human, animal, and environment are represented (Figure 21). Most of the isolates with an origin known come from poultry (4767), followed by human (2968), pigs (1454), and turkey (685). In addition, 422 isolates are labelled as from water or environmental samples. Nevertheless, a 30 percent of the samples did not specify the origin.

Figure 21. Distribution per origin of the *aac(3)-IV* positive isolates in the NCBI NDARO database.

In terms of location where the isolates were taken, *aac(3)-IV* seems to be already worldwide spread (Figure 22). The country that presents the greatest number of isolates is United States, with 8729 (a 49.01 percent of them), followed by China with 3696 (20.75 percent). In Europe, the countries that account for the most isolates are United Kingdom and Germany, with 631 and 178 respectively (3.54 and 1 percent).

Figure 22. Global distribution of the *aac(3)-IV* positive isolates in the NCBI NDARO database.

General discussion

Aminoglycosides have emerged as a great alternative in the current times of antimicrobial resistance, as new molecules are already in the drug development track. However, acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases threaten to render useless all the efforts. Prevalence of this resistance mechanism is still low in clinical isolates in Europe (Castanheira *et al.*, 2018). However, our results suggest something completely different, as a 7% of the Spanish metagenomic projects analysed present at least one of these enzymes. In contrast, while *armA* and *rmtB* are the most prevalent enzymes in clinical samples (Wachino *et al.*, 2020), less abundant methyltransferases like *rmtD*, *rmtF* or *npmA* seem to be commonly found in different complex environments. Of special interest is the latter, as it has been seen in different settings including humans, animals, and the environment. However, in the literature is considered one of the least abundant methyltransferases, as it has been barely reported (Wachino *et al.*, 2007; Al Seikh *et al.*, 2014; Zhao *et al.*, 2017; Sefidan *et al.*, 2019, Marsh *et al.*, 2019). The genetic context of the gene in the metagenomic samples suggest that bacteria of the Order Eubacteriales play an important role in the maintenance of the gene in the gut microbiome. This agrees with the latest observations of *npmA*, as it has been seen highly associated to *Clostridioides difficile* (Marsh *et al.*, 2019). As it is not the same environment and *npmA* seems to be associated with mobile genetic elements, all together suggests that the gene could be mobilised from closely related bacteria of *C. difficile* to the final environment where it has been reported.

Novel variants of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases have been found in the metagenomic samples. For example, in *npmA* we have confirmed that the critical residues for the methylation activity provided by the gene are maintained (Husain *et al.*, 2011; Dunkle *et al.*, 2014), so it is expected to be functional genes, but needs to be tested *in vitro* for the complete confirmation. It seems that the gene has a different function in their original host rather than antimicrobial resistance. This makes sense as aminoglycosides require oxygen to develop its function and the genetic contexts where the gene is found point out at anaerobic bacteria. This can be linked to the origin of the gene, that is still a topic of discussion in the 16S rRNA methyltransferase. For a long time, it has been proposed that aminoglycoside-producing bacteria might be the origin of these genes (Wachino *et al.*, 2020), but due to the GC content and our latest findings it seems that the probability of have the origin in an Eubacteriales bacteria is more plausible.

In addition, the prevalence rates observed could be underestimated. Targeted metagenomics not only helped us confirm the presence of these genes in an assembly approach but assisted us in the understanding of real prevalence. Since the relative abundance of these genes in shotgun metagenomic samples is low, some samples appeared to not harbour the resistance genes. However, after application of targeted metagenomics in the same samples we saw that initially negative samples turned positive, remarking for example that *npmA* them might be virtually present in all pig samples.

Metagenomics are a great source of information. In our project we have seen that metagenomics unravel an unknown persistence of low spread 16S rRNA methyltransferases in complex environments. However, common metagenomic analysis failed in unravelling the concrete reservoirs where the resistance genes are maintained. Binning approach seemed to be including *npmA* in some bins with good completion rates, but as was already suggested (Vollmers *et al.*, 2022), high completeness and low contamination are sometimes potentially misleading. Application of refinement tools reduce the mistakes introduced by binning tools and in our case left us without a single *npmA* positive bin.

Here is where fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH) comes into play. We decided to modify this technique to mark *npmA* to be able to discover the bacterial reservoirs that harbours it. This coupled to fluorescence assisted cell sorting (FACS) can separate individual cells carrying *npmA* to be able to precisely identify where it hides and guide future culture attempts of the reservoirs. Our results with *Escherichia coli* cells show promising results, but application of environmental samples might not be as straightforward. In our system, the *npmA* gene was in multiple copies and was actively transcribed, which produced a stronger signal as more fluorescent molecules were bound. In its native setting, we do not know in how many copies it is maintained or if it is actively expressed by the cells, which will influence our capacity of detection.

Apramycin has been proposed as the next antibiotic to be released to fight gram negative infections in humans. The few enzymes known conferring resistance to it, coupled with the less toxic effects shown in comparison with other aminoglycosides, make apramycin an attractive candidate. In addition, the results shown in our work suggest that apramycin use does not entail a major reconfiguration of the gut microbiome and does not show a dysbiosis effect as the diversity of taxonomic units in the apramycin treated farms was not detectably altered, which is a great characteristic for an antibiotic.

In contrast, the increase in diversity of resistance genes and the similar composition of the resistance gene content between the treated farms shows that apramycin use plays an important role in selecting for resistant bacteria. The fact that not only apramycin resistance genes appear to be more abundant

after apramycin uses points out to the contribution of mobile genetic elements, such as plasmids, in the spread of resistance genes. As these genetic elements commonly present resistance genes to various antibiotics even from different antimicrobial families, the use of any of these antibiotics can help for their selection. In our analyses, we see that *aac(3)-IV*, the most prevalent mechanism of resistance to apramycin known, appear highly associated to other resistance determinant, *aph(4)-Ia*. This latter gene is not very clinically relevant, as it is known that confers only resistance to hygromycin (Stogios *et al.*, 2011), but it increases the spectrum of antibiotics that can select for *aac(3)-IV*. In addition, the genetic context of *aac(3)-IV* also suggest that it can be embedded in plasmids frequently found in Enterobacteriaceae family members, where it has been shown to be associated with other amoxicillin and doxycycline resistance determinants, as well as to other aminoglycosides (Zhang *et al.*, 2009). This fact can contribute to the maintenance of the gene in the gut microbiome even when apramycin was not used. Furthermore, the insertion sequences flanking the gene and the different genetic contexts where it can be found suggest transposition events that can lead to bacterial host expansion and, therefore, contributing to its maintenance. Apart from species of the Enterobacteriaceae family, it seems based in our results that *aac(3)-IV* has some association with *Corynebacterium* or several species from the Enterococcales Order. These bacterial species can be commonly found on the poultry litter (Brooks *et al.*, 2010), what supports the fact that all poultry farms sampled showed the presence of the resistance gene, as these species with high environmental survivability can be acting as reservoirs.

Aac(3)-IV is considered the most prevalent mechanism of resistance to apramycin. A similar analysis to the one performed in our study estimated a prevalence of 0.69 percent of *aac(3)-IV* in all the isolates of the NDARO database in 2020 (Plattner *et al.*, 2020). Now, the number has almost duplicate in the period of two years. Keeping in mind the scarce of sequences of non-pathogenic bacteria in the databases, the circulating number of *aac(3)-IV* prior its clinical application in humans is underestimated. Massive application of the antibiotic in humans, seen that it promotes apramycin resistance genes selection, can render apramycin ineffective in a short time.

Overall, our analysis show that apramycin possess positive traits that make it attractive to enter human antimicrobial arsenal. However, we observed that apramycin use select for apramycin resistance genes that are more prevalent that appear in the literature and the databases. Nevertheless, our study included different Spanish farms that were only grouped based on the use of apramycin, but other factors that could influence our results have not been taken into consideration, as the variables can be infinite. The results obtained just show a trend that needs to be further explored via in vivo experiments to confirm the conclusions taken.

6. Conclusions and Future work and perspectives

The work performed in the frame of the METAPRO PhD doctoral project has reinforced the idea that acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases are a mechanism to look out now that aminoglycosides will be used more in human settings. Our data show that the prevalence of these enzymes is highly overlooked and that uncultured bacteria might play a role in their maintenance in the gut microbiome. Interestingly, we found that *npmA*, one of the least observed 16S rRNA methyltransferases, it is commonly found in humans, animals, and even in environmental samples. This finding is rather surprising, as it is the methyltransferase with the largest resistance spectrum known, and the fact that is already present worldwide and in different origins might make this gene problematic in the future, especially since apramycin is being tested to be used in humans. Sadly, the low abundance of this gene

in the settings where we find and the association to mobile genetic elements that we can see in the few contigs assembled make impossible to know which exact bacterium harbours it with conventional metagenomic approaches, that based on our result might be different in the different environments where it was found. The combination of FISH and single-cell genomics might help fill the gaps that our metagenomic analysis left. In one of our studies, we proposed a method that might be suitable for the detection of these reservoirs in the different samples. Due to the time limitations of this project, results on that behalf cannot be presented yet but will follow.

Targeted metagenomics using a resistance gene capturing platform has been of great utility to get a better picture of how widespread some of the 16S rRNA methyltransferases are and to confirm via assembly that the genes are there. For example, *npmA* has been shown to be present in all the pig samples tested. Since with shotgun metagenomics only two out of eight were detected in a low amount, it is logical to think that, depending on the sequencing depth of the project, the gene can be undetected even when it is present. More studies using this platform will enlighten to what extent *npmA* is a common component of the pig gut microbiota.

Finally, we explored the effect of the use of apramycin in a poultry model. Apramycin seems to be very promising, as it has not an apparent effect on the bacterial composition in the gut. However, it seems to largely select for apramycin resistance genes, like *npmA* and *aac(3)-IV*. The former we already saw that is already part of the human microbiome, so an application of apramycin might favour an increase in its abundance, and the latter is already present in clinical isolates associated to plasmids, so apramycin can be rendered ineffective in a short time after its release for human medicine.

Obviously, we mainly centred our work in *npmA*, but the other 16S rRNA methyltransferases found in our project deserve to be investigated, so following projects to further evaluate them will come.

7. PhD project self-evaluation

Despite a slow start due to pandemic restrictions, we believe that METAPRO has met the two major objectives that we considered in our proposal. In our work we have showed that plazomicin resistance determinants are more prevalent as genomic studies and databases show and we have explored new methodologies for the detection of the reservoirs of such resistance mechanisms. However, to reach this point we needed to do a few adjustments during the project.

Initially focused on plazomicin, we believed that the aminoglycoside class has more to offer than just this compound. We found that there are many projects focused on obtaining semi-synthetic derivatives from all aminoglycoside subclasses, as well as clinical trials to release apramycin for human use. Therefore, we decided to target in METAPRO the resistance mechanism that can prevent the action of the old and the next generation aminoglycosides, the acquired 16S rRNA, methyltransferases, as well as deepening the understanding of the effect of the use of apramycin, as it may be the next antibiotic released to the market.

The project was initially based on collecting samples, but COVID made unable this approach for a long time. Therefore, we shifted our focus to the metagenomic projects already available. We limited ourselves to Spain, to mimic the sampling that was initially report. Rapidly, we saw that 16S rRNA methyltransferases are more prevalent than it is thought and that the normal carriers of this enzymes

are not species from the Enterobacteriaceae family but rather commensal non-pathogenic bacteria from the gut of humans and animals. Here we decided to change another task proposed, that was the isolation of enterobacteria carrying plazomicin resistance genes to isolating commensal non-pathogenic bacteria from samples where the resistance genes of interest were spotted. In addition, at this point we were able to gather some samples from different animal origins that confirmed the *in silico* results.

At this point, since conventional culture approaches were not suitable for our purpose, we asked for a Short-Term Mission to try to achieve this using a combination of fluorescence in situ hybridisation and single-cell genomics. These experiments are still ongoing, and we expect to have results during this year.

We also proposed a sampling in the United Kingdom, but we believe that the information obtained from there will be limited and, therefore, not compensate the money and the effort. Then, we exchange the task for a global analysis of one of the resistance genes found in our first metagenomic study, as there is a lot of information in the databases that could have been helpful than a random sampling.

We are still working on analyses and experiments that complement what it has been presented in this report and we believe that more projects can come after this one to fill the gaps that the time limitation has not let us explore.

8. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

Please fill the tables below. If a delay is due to the COVID-19 crisis, please add a comment. If there are no corrections required then no action is necessary.

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*
METAPRO	D1	Questionnaire on farm management, biosecurity, health and antibiotic use in livestock farming	M37	M40		
METAPRO	D2	Thesis manuscript	M63	-	Delayed. There is still some work that needs to be performed to complete the PhD project	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
METAPRO	M1	Spanish sampling design	M32	M65	Yes	Due to COVID, access to samples was denied for a long time, so we focused on the metagenomic projects already accessible through databases.

METAPRO	M2	Spanish sampling execution	M35	M65	Yes	Spanish metagenomic projects were gathered and analysed. In addition, some animal samples were collected.
METAPRO	M3	Metagenome sequencing of the Spanish sampling	M39	M65	Yes	Some samples were sequenced but they did not offer more information than the one provided by the sequences already deposited in the databases.
METAPRO	M4	Bacterial isolation and WGS from Spanish sampling	M39	-	Ongoing	Several attempts have been made to isolate the bacteria harbouring the resistance genes of interest, but we have not succeed yet. We are exploring new methodologies (FISH + SCG) to isolate the reservoirs.
METAPRO	M5	Design of United Kingdom sampling	M42	-	No	We decided not to invest more time on a second sampling. This task was modified for an analysis of one plazomicin resistance gene in all the metagenomic projects in the world.
METAPRO	M6	United Kingdom sampling execution	M45	-	No	Refer to M5
METAPRO	M7	Metagenomic sequencing of the United Kingdom sampling	M48	-	No	Refer to M5
METAPRO	M8	Bacterial isolation and WGS from United Kingdom sampling	M48	-	No	Refer to M5
METAPRO	M9	Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from both samplings	M48	-	Ongoing	There is a lot of information gathered and we are still trying to add a few more analysis and

						experiments that complement all the work done.
METAPRO	M10	Guideline for early detection of plazomicin resistance determinants to preserve plazomicin for human clinical use	M57	-	No	In the end will not be performed.
METAPRO	M11	Thesis manuscript	M63	-	No	PhD project will be continued for another year to finish all the experiments and analyses that are planned.
METAPRO	M12	Thesis defence	M66	-	No	Refer to M11

9. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (global, EU, national or regional) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), national and international surveillance programmes.

FARMED: Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests (<https://onehealth.eip.eu/jrp-farmed/>). Since the objectives and the techniques of both projects are similar, the candidate took part actively in the tasks performed at UCM associated to this project, performing long read metagenomics from a set of samples from environmental origin.

AVANT: Alternatives to Veterinary Antimicrobials (<https://avant-project.eu/>). The student has been also involved in some of the analysis performed in the project focused on the development and test of alternatives to antimicrobials.

DAMR-Una Europa: “Disseminate antimicrobial resistance knowledge and the use of whole genome sequencing on relevant bacterial pathogens during COVID-19 world emergency (<https://fredepasquali.wixsite.com/damr-project>). The student took part in this project teaching a webinar on metagenomics and collaborating on the sequencing of bacterial pathogens and their genomic analysis.

10. Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders

EFFORT: Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission (<http://www.effort-against-amr.eu/>). The group participated actively in the EFFORT project and its activities and resources are the foundation of the present research project.

11. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

Apart from the obvious, that is funding the PhD project, being part of the One Health EJP has offered a lot of alternatives for the best development of the research that we were carrying out. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meetings have been an excellent opportunity to present the work done and discuss it with many different top level European researchers not always from our field, that have enlarged our point of view. Having the possibility to present posters and oral talks in the ASM has contributed enormously to the development of the communication skills of the PhD student, quality that is necessary in science. In addition, being part of the consortium has given the possibility to participate in numerous activities organised by the One Health EJP, like summer schools, webinars, or a Short-Term Mission. Especially important has been the latter, that has resulted in the collaboration with another European group outside of the consortium, where the exchange of ideas has taken place and where we have taken our research to a whole new level.

12. Transferrable skills and Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Workshop “Aspectos epidemiológicos y estadísticos de un trabajo de investigación”	Epidemiology and Statistics	03-04/03/2020, 02/06/2020, 09/06/2020	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universidad Complutense de Madrid
qPCR technician and analyst at Lab UCM COVID-19	COVID-19, qPCR	15/03/2020 – 01/06/2020	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course “Textos científicos con LaTeX”	LaTeX software	27/05/2020 – 16/09/2020	Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Biosafety seminar	Microbiology and Biosafety	14/07/2020	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universidad Complutense de Madrid
One Health EJP Summer School 2020	One Health	17-28/08/2020	Wageningen University
Teaching of Practical classes in the Veterinary Medicine Degree	Microbiology and Immunology	Academic Course 2019/2020	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universidad Complutense de Madrid
VISAVET Journal Club	Microbiology	Academic Course 2019/2020	VISAVET
Resistomap Webinar Series	Antibiotic Resistance and Environment	25/08/2020 – 24/11/2020	Resistomap
Course “Análisis de datos con Phyton”	Phyton	14/09/2020 – 11/12/2020	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
OHEJP FARMED Meeting	Metagenomics	29/10/2020	Sciensano
K-mer alignment training workshop	Metagenomics	6/11/2020	Technical University of Denmark
Webinar “Jornada Complutense sobre Resistencia a Antibióticos”	Antibiotic Resistance	23/11/2020	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
MicroMundo Symposium	AMR	27-28 th /04/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Webinar Series ‘Jornadas sobre la Carrera Investigadora’	Scientific Research	14/01/2021 – 29/04/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course ‘Hojas de Cálculo con Excel I’	Excel	15/03/2021 – 30/06/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course ‘Hojas de Cálculo con Excel II’	Excel	14/06/2021 – 29/10/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Workshop ‘Bioinformatics tools and methods for antimicrobial resistance’	AMR	15/10/2021	PH4GE, JPIAMR and CLIMB-BIG-DATA
BioinfoCAM meeting	Bioinformatics	21/10/2021	SEBiBC
VI Jornadas de Bioinformática	Bioinformatics	24-25/02/2022	Universidad de Granada
Jornada “One Health, Salud Humana, Animal y Medioambiental. Impacto económico y social”	One Health	24/03/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course “Aprende a manejar R y RStudio”	R language	30/05/2022 – 03/06/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course “Introducción a la estadística como herramienta metodológica para la investigación”	Statistics	07-15/06/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course “Visualización de datos con Python”	Python language	13/06/2022 – 30/09/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
One Health EJP Final School 2022	One Health	05-07/12/2022	University of Surrey
One Health EJP Short Term Mission	AMR	01/03/23 – 31/12/23	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology

13. Ethical Reviews

Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments PhD Project Supervisor, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2020
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<p>Biological samples The beneficiary must confirm that no Human and/or Animal samples will be collected for further analysis.</p> <p>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects Considering the area of work, the beneficiary must re-confirm that there are no environmental or H&S Aspects.</p>	<p>Biological samples The intention is to use sewage from the different origins; therefore, the samples will not be collected directly from humans or animals.</p> <p>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects Our research will not cause any harm to humans, animals or the environment; and will not involve endangered fauna or protected areas.</p>	
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14. Scientific Publications

Publication date	Publication title	Authors	DOI reference	Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? *please specify embargo length	Is it a Gold Open Access?

15. Additional Outputs

16. Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Interbacterial mobilization of aac(3)-IV in the gut microbiome. *Oral presentation*. XIII Reunión del Grupo de Microbiología Molecular of the Spanish Society of Microbiology, Granada, Spain. 7-9th September 2022.

Metagenomic analysis of the effects of apramycin on the microbiome. *Oral presentation*. VIII VETINDOC – PhDay Complutense 2022, Madrid, Spain. June 2022.

Matamoros, B. R., Serna, C., Moyano, G., Wedel, E., Pulido-Vadillo, M., Montero, N., & Gonzalez-Zorn, B. (2022). Metagenomic analysis reveals that apramycin restructures the resistome and favors interbacterial spread of aac(3)-IV gene. *Poster presentation*. 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID), Lisbon, Portugal. April 2022.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561960>

Metagenomic sequencing analysis of the effects of apramycin in the poultry gut microbiome. *Oral presentation*. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, Orvieto, Italy. 11-13th April 2022.

Matamoros, B. R., Serna, C., Hernández, A., Montero, N., Garcia, M., Blanco, J. L., & Gonzalez-Zorn, B. (2021). First report of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferase armA in an *Enterobacter hormaechei* ST171 isolated from a horse. *Poster presentation*. 31st European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID). 9th July 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561938>

Matamoros, B. R., Serna, C., Hernández, A., Montero, N., Garcia, M., Blanco, J. L., & Gonzalez-Zorn, B. (2021). One Health: ArmA and *Enterobacter hormaechei* ST171. *Oral presentation*. XXVIII Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Microbiología (SEM). 28th June 2021.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561901>

Matamoros, B. R., Serna, C., Delgado-Blas, J. F., Wedel, E., Montero, N., Garcia, M. E., Blanco, J. L., & Gonzalez-Zorn, B. (2021). Acquired 16 rRNA methyltransferase ArmA maintained for a decade in a veterinary hospital via an IncR plasmid. *Poster presentation*. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, Copenhagen Denmark & online. 9-11th June 2021.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561877>

Matamoros, B. R., Glaser, P., La Ragione, R. M., & Gonzalez-Zorn, B. (2020). METAPRO: Metagenomics and genomic approaches for the prevention of the spread of plazomicin resistance in humans, animals and the environment. *Poster presentation*. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2020, online. 27-29th May 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561834>

OHEJP blog post in June 2022 for the “One Health EJP PhD Life” campaign: [A day in the life of Bosco Rodríguez Matamoros](#)

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Some of the discoveries of the project with relationship to apramycin have been discussed with apramycin and apramycin-derivatives promoters and developers to design the best strategy possible to maintain the efficacy of the compounds.

17. One Health impact

Antimicrobial resistance is one of the fields where the importance of One Health can be easily seen. In this doctoral project, we have been focused on the resistance to an important antibiotic family, the aminoglycosides. Both World Health Organisation (WHO) and World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) have categorised this class as critically necessary. Nevertheless, there are some resistance mechanisms that already compromise the application of the aminoglycosides, even the next-generation ones. The acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases modify the target of the aminoglycosides, so even in the case of the new aminoglycoside modifications that are in progress to be released in a close future, the resistance is conferred to the bacteria that expresses them.

Since the prevalence of these resistance enzymes is thought to be low, in this project we have evaluated their abundance in complex environments and in non-clinical settings, where the role of non-pathogenic bacteria in the maintenance and dissemination of antimicrobial resistance genes can be assessed. There we have found a high prevalence of 16S rRNA methyltransferases in the gut microbiota of human, pigs, and chickens. From our data seems that unknown commensal bacteria may be the carriers, but association to mobile genetic elements is already seen, so it is not illogical to think that these resistances genes that are maintained in the gut of potentially every pig or chicken could be mobilised to a pathogenic bacterium and jeopardise the application of this antibiotic class. We have the perfect opportunity for the monitoring of these resistance genes before we cannot control them anymore.

In this work we propose that complex microbial communities are the potential origin of some of the resistance genes that we see in our clinics. Surveillances through metagenomics and single cell genomics are still not in a point where implementation can be completely feasible, but investing in this direction may be a good approach to tackle the next widespread resistance genes before they even enter our clinical settings. For example, the One Health EJP project FARMED aimed to do that on site and some promising results were obtained from it.

Finally, we have evaluated the role of apramycin in the selection of resistance genes. Since apramycin has gained a lot of attention lately and a great effort is being made to release it for human use, we believe that more studies are required from an antimicrobial resistance perspective before the final decisions are taken. Apramycin is approved in animals, which offered us a perfect setting for this study. In the farms that we analysed we saw that the use of apramycin heavily selects for apramycin genes. These genes seem already be widespread in every One Health setting that you can think of, so, apramycin application in humans could lead to a quick inefficacy of the compound. More studies are needed to evaluate this selection phenomenon before

apramycin is approved, because there is a lot of effort and money in the table that could have little return.

18. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2020 (poster)		
Date:	27 th –29 th May 2020		
Place:	ONLINE		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	X
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	750	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Three Minute Thesis Competition		
Date:	28 th May 2020		
Place:	ONLINE		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	X
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	

<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	750	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP Three Minute Competition 2021 and poster presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>10th June 2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Copenhagen/ONLINE</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	X
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	X
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education,</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Seminar presentation 'Identificación y caracterización molecular de mecanismos de resistencia a antibióticos emergentes'</i>		
Date:	<i>12th May 2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universidad Complutense de</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	X

<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education,</i>	50+	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>31st European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID) + Poster Presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>9th- 12th July 2021</i>		
Place:	<i>ONLINE</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	X
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education,</i>	14000+	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>XXVIII Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Microbiología (SEM) + Poster Presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>28th June – 2nd July 2021</i>		
Place:	<i>ONLINE</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	X
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	

Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education,	900+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Oral presentation at One Health Annual Scientific Meeting 2022		
Date:	11 – 13 th April 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550	Media	
Industry	10	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	10		

Name of the activity:	3 Minute Thesis Presentation at One Health Annual Scientific Meeting 2022
Date:	11 – 13 th April 2022

Place:	Orvieto, Italy		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550	Media	
Industry	10	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	10		

Name of the activity:	Poster presentation at 32 nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID)		
Date:	23-26 th April 2022		
Place:	Lisbon, Portugal		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number

<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	15000	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Oral presentation at VIII Jornada VETINDOC – 6º PhDay Complutense</i>		
Date:	<i>30th June 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Madrid, Spain</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	50+	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Oral presentation at XIII Reunión del Grupo Especializado Microbiología Molecular de la SEM</i>		
Date:	<i>7-9th September 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Granada, Spain</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	

Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	200	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

19. Bibliography

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